

Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

D5.2: Intermediate Evaluation

WP5 – Pilot Operation and Evaluation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649493

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	649493	Acronym	STEP	
Full Project Title	Societal and political engagement of young people in environmental issues			
Start Date	1 st June 2015	Duration	30 months	
Project URL	www.step4youth.eu			
Deliverable	D 5.2 – Intermediate Evaluation			
Work Package	WP 5 – Pilot Operation and Evaluation			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	31 May 2017	Actual	12 July 2017
Nature	R - Report	Dissemination Level	P – Public	
Lead Beneficiary	University of Abertay			
Responsible Authors	Dr Paula Forbes			
Contributions from	Dr Ken Scott-Brown, Dr Stefano De Paoli, Maria Vogiatzi, Christodoulos Keratidis			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
1.0	/04/2017	Draft		Paula Forbes
2.0	11/06/2017	Draft	Added results of PM interviews & contributions from Draxis	Maria Vogiatzi, Christodoulos Keratidis
3.0	07/07/2017	Final	Amended after internal review	Sotiris Diplaris

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Executive Summary

This Intermediate Evaluation Deliverable reports on the progress to date of the Pilot partners use of the STEP platform in carrying out eParticipation activities with young people across the various European regions involved in the project. A combination of qualitative and quantitative methods have been utilised to evaluate the platform with the end users, including surveys and interviews. This approach has been effective in highlighting both the positive and negative aspects of the platform itself and how it is being used.

Early results from both young people and Policy Makers are evaluating the platform positively for most aspects, including effectively having their voice heard by the relevant person, attractiveness of the platform, help/support. Aspects such as the platform being able to get other Young People (YP) interested in important environmental issues and seeing the ideas from other YP were also rated well. Ease of use was mostly positive, but some aspects such as young people knowing how to make a post for the first time could be improved upon. Interviews with end users gave us some useful insights about their use of the platform and any issues that they had encountered. These findings are discussed in more detail in the results section. Recommendations for improvement are also proposed in Chapter 3.

Intended audience is primarily the people involved in the project but this deliverable may be of interest to others carrying out eParticipation activities as it highlights some of the issues that may be encountered and suggests actions for resolution.

1. Evaluating eParticipation

The evaluation of eParticipation efforts and pilots is of critical importance for identifying successful eParticipation practices, processes and systems appropriate for achieving specific participation objectives in specific situations and contexts, and for improving eParticipation practices, processes and systems (Loukis, 2012). The literature discussing the various aspects important to the Evaluation of eParticipation was presented in D5.1 (Definition of STEP Pilots and Evaluation Methodology).

eParticipation can only work effectively when citizens actually engage with the tools and use them. Applications need to be designed with high functionality to enable citizen participation in a convenient and efficient way. This requires understanding who the users are and what they will be doing on the site (Coleman et al., 2008). Appropriate and high-level functionality will match citizens needs better and encourage them to use the platform more, thus increasing levels of eParticipation. Loukis, (2012) states that two basic categories exist regarding evaluation; a) 'Is it doing things right?' and b) 'Is it doing the right things?' Our evaluation methodologies intend to identify both of these aspects and to ensure a successful platform as an end result of the project.

In this report we will concentrate on the issues encountered, and how we are focusing our efforts to enable the Pilot partners to reach their objectives of including a large number of young people in environmental policy making via the STEP platform.

1.1 *STEP's Approach to Evaluating eParticipation*

As explained in D5.1 we have mapped our evaluation process onto the STEP measurable project objectives whilst also considering evaluation methodologies described in the literature. A combination of qualitative and quantitative techniques is currently being used to evaluate the experience of all stakeholders.

1.2 *User Survey Methodology*

Our main rationale in developing the surveys was to ensure we successfully evaluate the STEP project Success Indicators and for those that require user input (ie cannot be measured through automated tracking), to ask clear Likert scale questions that will produce a number of quantitative results as well as some more in depth open-ended questions.

The surveys can be viewed in the Appendices of D5.1. Separate surveys were developed for the different end user types, ie Young People and Policy Maker and we also developed shorter surveys specific to the various eParticipation processes being trialed in the Pilots.

Surveys have now been translated into the local language by the Pilot Partners and some have now been distributed to those people engaging with the STEP platform dialogues at this point in time. Future timescales for the deployment of the short surveys will be at the end of each of the short Pilot studies (Dialogues with Young People). A final study Survey distribution is proposed for Month 27 in order to allow sufficient time for participants to respond and for the data to be analysed and reported in the deliverable. Further, larger scale survey deployment will be carried out by all Pilots to ensure effective evaluation for the end of the project and the final evaluation deliverable.

1.3 *Interviews with Key Stakeholders*

A number of structured interviews have been conducted with stakeholders from the Pilots (see appendix A for interview questions). These interviews have proved very effective in highlighting both the positive and any negative issues encountered when using the STEP platform. Further interviews with both young people and policy makers will be conducted for the duration of the project to ensure sufficient feedback is obtained and that their feedback is acted upon to improve the platform.

2. *User Evaluation Results*

2.1 *Status of STEP pilots*

According to the deliverable 5.1 the STEP pilot was scheduled to be implemented between months 18 and 30 (November 2016 - November 2017), and it was broken down into 4 phases.

🕒 *1st phase*

The first phase focused on the training of the public officers on the STEP platform and it was implemented in month 18. During this phase STEP's technical partners organized two webinars for all the pilot partners, as well as separate conference calls with each one of them, in order to familiarize them with the use of the features of the platform. Additionally, a workshop dedicated to STEP pilots was organized by the technical partners in the framework of STEP's 5th project meeting in Prague. During the workshop, all pilots had the opportunity to create scenarios (petitions, ideas, consultations, questionnaires, etc), as well as collections with the use of the social media monitoring tool under the guidance of the technical team.

🕒 *2nd phase*

The 2nd phase of the pilot took place between months 19 and 20. All along this phase each pilot partner established a core group of users and performed an internal test on the STEP platform. A dialogue under the name "User Feedback on STEP Platform" was created in step.green and all partners were invited to share their feedback and report any issues, problems and bugs. The ultimate goal of this phase was to ensure that the platform meets users' needs and is ready to go public. The "User Feedback on STEP Platform" dialogue is still open and can be accessed not only by all partners, but also by users in case they want to report any issue or problem they encounter.

🕒 *3rd phase*

The 3rd phase, which includes the pilot implementation, has started and pilot partners have already uploaded a number of dialogues onto the platform. The STEP platform was launched to the general public by the pilot partners in order to be tested by young citizens in real context. The launching of the STEP platform was initially planned in M21 (February 2017) and dialogues were uploaded on the platform by the pilots at this time period. STEP Platform with its main functionalities was available and ready as planned in February 2017. However, due to some minor bugs, like broken links to download mobile apps, invitation email issues, translation quality issues and lack of tutorials for PA administrators to manage their dialogues, created a short delay to the launching of the platform. These issues were resolved and the pilots started their official dialogues in March 2017. Generally, the pilot partners followed the initial plan and adapted it according to their special needs and the timeframe that was more convenient to them. All pilots have organized a number of events and have participated in various others in order to present the STEP solution in their areas. Furthermore, they have implemented additional online, as well as offline promotional activities, which are described in D7.5 2nd Report on Dissemination Activities. This Chapter describes each local pilot operation in terms of dialogues uploaded, evaluation of completed dialogues and number of citizens registered in each pilot. Additionally, this chapter presents the revised plan of dialogues of the pilot partners and the changes in each pilot.

🕒 *4th phase*

The 4th phase which refers to the evaluation of the pilots is an ongoing one, and takes place along the pilot implementation (M18-M30). The pilots' evaluation will assess the usability of the STEP platform, and the effectiveness and impact of the project in embedding open engagement in public sector processes.

2.1.1 Region of Crete

The Region of Crete has uploaded a number of Environmental Impact Assessment studies on the STEP platform. Apart from the studies, three additional dialogues about environmental issues have been uploaded onto the platform. The table below presents the dialogues brought under public consultation until the end of May 2017 (M24).

Issue	Scenario	Type	Start	End	No of participants
Environmental Impact study for the clay mine in the Regional Unit of Rethymno	E-petition	Public	1/02/2017	1/03/2017	6
Environmental Impact study for the Digea's antenna located in Sitia, Lasithi	E-petition	Public	1/02/2017	1/03/2017	6
Environmental Impact study of the project for the protection of the road in Kourtalioti forge from rocks falling	E-petition	Public	14/12/2016	14/6/2017	25
Environmental Impact study for the Digea's antenna located in Amari, Rethymno	E-petition	Public	1/02/2017	3/04/2017	22
Environmental Impact study for the hotel "Castri Village" in Palaiokastros, Lasithi	E-petition	Public	1/02/2017	3/04/2017	21
Environmental Impact study for the unit of production of biogas and electricity in Heraklion	E-petition	Public	1/02/2017	3/04/2017	23
Environmental Impact study for the hybrid unit for electricity production located in Rethymno and Lasithi	E-petition	Public	1/02/2017	3/04/2017	31
Environmental Impact study for the sea based fish aquaculture unit in Lasithi	E-petition	Public	1/02/2017	3/04/2017	20
Environmental Impact study for the wastewater treatment unit of Sougia, Chania	E-petition	Public	7/03/2017	12/04/2017	13
Environmental Impact study for the waste management factory in Heraklion	E-petition	Public	1/02/2017	3/04/2017	22

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Environmental Impact study for the Electrical interconnection between Crete and Peloponese	E-petitions	Public	21/3/2017	30/4/2017	5
Energy savings and greenhouse gas emission reductions	Call for ideas	Public	23/3/2017	31/7/2017	37
Environmental Impact study for a new unit for the incineration of dead livestock and pet animals as well as animal by-products	E petition	Public	18/4/2017	2/6/2017	7
Environmental Impact study for the improvement of the road Papagiannakides –Armenoi	E petition	Public	18/4/2017	28/5/2017	0
Environmental Impact study for the wastewater treatment unit of Kalamafkas, Lasithi	E petition	Public	18/4/2017	2/05/2017	0
Environmental Impact study for the wastewater treatment unit of Palaikastro, Lasithi	E petition	Public	18/4/2017	2/06/2017	21
Environmental Impact study for the Digea's antenna located in Ierapetra	E petition	Public	18/4/2017	2/06/2017	6
Call for ideas for the Southern Road of Crete	Call for ideas	Public	20/4/2017	31/12/2017	7
Make your everyday life greener	Call for ideas	Public	20/4/2017	31/12/2017	2
Environmental Impact study for the hotel "ELEFThERIA", located in Agia Marina, Chania	E petition	Public	24/4/2017	2/6/2017	11
Environmental Impact study for a new hotel with 770 beds which will be built at Petre, Rethymno	E petition	Public	24/4/2017	4/6/2017	12
Call for Ideas about the Natura 2000 areas in Crete	Call for ideas	Public	18/05/2017	18/11/2017	18
Environmental consequences from the uncontrolled use of land	E petition	Public	11/05/2017	31/10/2017	4

Until the end of May 2017, the Region of Crete had used the STEP tool to bring 23 issues under public consultation. These issues were mainly Environmental Impact studies for private and public investments. So far, a pdf file (non-technical summary) for each study was uploaded on the platform. However, since pdf files are not accessible through the Android application, the Region of Crete decided that in the future will

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include additional information in the dialogue description. All the Environmental Studies are uploaded on the website of the Region of Crete and are linked with the STEP platform.

“As one notices in the table, the number of citizens who participate in Crete’s dialogues is quite low. This is probably because the Environmental Impact studies do not belong in the main areas of interest of young people. So far, not even one young person participated in the offline procedure of the consultation of the Environmental Impact studies. Generally, most studies do not attract the attention of public; it depends on the subject of the study, whether it refers to a new or an existing activity, a factory or a hotel, etc. The Region of Crete is not able to choose, or to define the topics of the Environmental Impact Assessment studied during the implementation of the pilot plan, so all of them will be uploaded on the platform.

It should be noted that even though there are not many comments on the studies, the Region of Crete believe that the online consultation procedure is quite important, since it is an easy way for citizens to find information about local projects and post their comments promptly and conveniently. Additionally, the STEP platform provides an easy and user friendly interface that helps young people to get familiar with the procedure and the concept of Environmental Studies, and gradually to feel more confidence to express their opinion. For that reason the Region of Crete decided that will not exclude such kinds of dialogues from the STEP platform.

As a mitigation plan, and in order to attract the interest of young people and come closer to them, in April 2017, the Region of Crete uploaded three dialogues concerning local environmental issues. Additional dialogues about general environmental topics are scheduled to be brought under public participation through STEP within the following months.

Twelve dialogues on Environmental Impact studies have been concluded so far. Citizens’ feedback has been taken into consideration during the consultation procedure. Additionally, for each study, a summary of the users’ feedback was included in the respective document that was sent to the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete in order to express a positive or negative opinion about the study. The dialogues that have been concluded are presented in the table below.

Dialogue	Brief Description
Environmental Impact study for the clay mine in the Regional Unit of Rethymno	This dialogue was created in order to further open the consultation procedure of the Environmental Impact Study of this specific activity to young people. The participants in the questionnaire was 6 and according to the results of the consultation procedure young people think that this kind of activity mostly influences the landscape.
Environmental Impact study for the Digea's antenna located in Sitia, Lasithi	The participants of this dialogue were 6 in total and no comments were posted. This dialogue intended to ask young people’s opinion on the most important impacts of the activity. The result showed that the young people think that this kind of activity mostly influences the landscape.
Environmental Impact study for the Digea's antenna located in Amari, Rethymno	The participants of this dialogue were 22 in total and one comment was posted regarding the necessity of this activity. This dialogue intended to ask young people’s opinion on the most important impacts of the activity. The result showed that young people think that this kind of activity mostly influences the landscape.
Environmental Impact study for the hotel "Catri Village" in Palaiokastros,	The citizens who participated in this dialogue were 21 and no comments or posts were made. . This dialogue intended to ask young

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Lasithi	people’s opinion on the most important impacts of a hotel. The result showed that the young people think waste water management is the most important environmental issue.
Environmental Impact study for the unit of production of biogas and electricity in Heraklion	The participants in this dialogue were 23. No comments or posts were made. The questionnaire of this dialogue would indicate the most important impacts of the biogas unit. The result showed that young people think waste water management is the most important environmental issue of the unit.
Environmental Impact study for the hybrid unit for electricity production located in Rethymno and Lasithi	31 citizens joined this dialogue. One comment was made but was not relevant to environmental impacts. The outcome of the questionnaire concerned the most important impacts of the hybrid unit. The result showed that the young people think that landscape deterioration is the main impact of the unit.
Environmental Impact study for the sea based fish aquaculture unit in Lasithi	20 citizens joined the dialogue, while no comments were made. The questionnaire of this dialogue intended to find out citizens’ opinion on the most important impacts of the unit. The result showed that young people think ecosystem balance deterioration is the main environmental impact of the unit.
Environmental Impact study for the wastewater treatment unit of Sougia, Chania	The goal of this dialogue was to check if young citizens are aware of the pollution problem in Sougia. According to the result of 13 questionnaires, young people think that the source of the pollution is not only the lack of wastewater treatment in the village of Sougia, but also the lack of wastewater treatment units in Palaiochora and Sfakia. An additional source of pollution are the ships. No comments were made in this dialogue, in order to take them into consideration in the report for the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete. However, in the document sent to the Committee there is a reference in the consultation made through STEP.
Environmental Impact study for the waste management factory in Heraklion	22 citizens participated in this dialogue, while no comments were made. The outcome of the questionnaire indicated that young people are aware that prevention of waste production should be a priority.
Environmental Impact study for the Electrical interconnection between Crete and Peloponese	The participants in this dialogue were 5 citizens. The questionnaire was focused on the impacts of the interconnection. The answers showed that young people believe that the interconnection of Crete with the rest of Greece will automatically invite additional renewable energy investments for the island and will reduce the operating hours of the thermal units.
Environmental Impact study for the improvement of the road Papagiannakides –Armenoi	This dialogue was created in order to further open the consultation procedure of the Environmental Impact Study of a new part of the road between the villages Papagiannakides and Armenoi in the Regional Unit of Lasithi. There were no comments on this dialogue.
Environmental Impact study for the	This dialogue was created in order to further open the consultation

<p>wastewater treatment unit of Kalamafkas, Lasithi</p>	<p>procedure of the Environmental Impact Study of the wastewater treatment unit in the area of Kalamafkas in Lasithi. There were no comments on this dialogue.</p>
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According to the table with the concluded dialogues above, one notices that the title “Environmental Impact study for the hybrid unit for electricity production located in Rethymno and Lasithi” has attracted the highest interest of the citizens. Additionally, the Region of Crete expects that the three dialogues on general environmental issues that have been recently uploaded on the platform, as well as the upcoming ones, will further attract the interest of young citizens and will eventually manage to increase the number of participants in the Pilot.

Additionally, the Region of Crete has recognized a number of strategies that have been taken into consideration and used more intensively in the following months in order to promote the dialogues more effectively. Such strategies are; the use of social media and especially Facebook, the establishment of synergies with environmental and youth associations that will support the dialogues, as well as the systematic use of online invitations that could be sent through the STEP platform. Crete’s pilot upcoming dissemination activities are described in D7.5 2nd Report on Dissemination Activities.

Initial Pilot Plan & Upcoming Dialogues:

The Region of Crete has applied the initial dialogues pilot plan with some slight changes in the timeframe; the pilot intends to proceed with this plan, and probably with some changes in the timeline, as it is indicated below. Some additional changes are under discussion and refer to the dialogues “Coastal Zone degradation” and “waste water reclamation and reuse”, which, are considered to be too technical, and probably too complicated for young people to participate. In this context there is a possibility that the dialogue about the Coastal Zone degradation will be excluded and a round table discussion will be organized for the “Waste water reclamation and reuse” dialogue.

Initial pilot plan with the environmental issues proposed to be brought in the STEP platform									
Project months	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29
Environmental issues									
<i>Environmental impact assessment consultation</i> There is a regular flow of 7 to 8 consultations per month. The timeframe for each consultation is 35 or 45 days.									
<i>Energy Conservation</i>									
<i>Water Management actions</i>									
<i>Protection of NATURA habitats and protected species</i>									
<i>Coastal Zone degradation</i>									
<i>Wastewater reclamation and reuse</i>									

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<i>Climate change</i>									
<i>Sustainable tourism, ecotourism</i>									

Updated Pilot Plan							
Project months	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	
<i>Environmental issues</i>							
<i>Environmental impact assessment consultation</i>							
Energy Conservation							
<i>Natura protection</i>							
<i>Make your daily life greener</i>							
<i>Environmental and other impacts of uncontrolled urban land use</i>							
<i>Water Management actions</i>							
<i>Sustainable tourism, ecotourism</i>							
<i>Climate change</i>							
<i>Waste water reclamation and reuse (round table)</i>							

Inclusion

The Region of Crete has created spots with computers available in the premises of each Regional Unit, which can be used by young people in order to access the platform. Additionally, 6 tablets and laptops were available during the Launch Events, so as all the participants to have the opportunity to use and explore the platform, even if they didn't own smartphones. Those tablets are available for all events that the Region of Crete participates or organizes.

2.1.2 Mollet del Vallès Municipality

STEP has become an important tool for Mollet del Valles Municipality. Prior to the launch of an environmental public dialogue, the Municipality creates a private one for the members of the City Council, in order to exchange views and ideas on the topic and set up the public dialogue in detail and more effectively. Additionally, before setting up a dialogue the Municipality organizes a meeting with the members of the core team and other experts with special knowledge on the issue to be published.

Dialogues at STEP platform					
Issue	Scenario	Type	Start	End	No of participants
Gallecs, your park: enjoy it!	Call for ideas	Public	24/02/2017	2/04/2017	86
Mollet Blossomed Village (city parks)	Call for ideas	Public	23/02/2017	19/03/2017	32
City Council Area (intranet for Municipality's highest participation body)	Call for ideas	Private	15/03/2017	19/12/2017	32
Select a project; make your allocation of 100.000 euros of public investment. Participative budget.	Call for ideas	Private	22/05/2017	4/07/2017	350
Urban Garden Can Borrell	E-petition	Public	15/03/2017	30/04/2017	113
Olympic Games in Mollet 25 years after	Call for ideas	Private	14/03/2017	31/12/2017	2
City Plan for Young People (intranet)	Innovation	Private	2/03/2017	31/12/2017	31
Public space, help us to improve the city	E-petition	Public	16/03/2017	31/12/2017	25
City Plan for young people	Innovation	Private	02/03/2017	31/12/2017	31
Mollet Vila Florida	Call for ideas	Public	23/02/2017	02/04/2017	32
Rumours prevention	E-petition and ideas	Public	14/05/2017	15/11/2017	22
Electric vehicle in Mollet	Innovation	Public	08/05/2017	29/05/2017	2

Three dialogues have been concluded and the Municipality of Mollet has developed a plan to exploit users' feedback for each dialogue. The table below provides all relevant information.

Dialogue	Brief Description
Gallecs, your park. Come and enjoy it!	In this dialogue Mollet del Valles Municipality invited citizens to answer a questionnaire about the park and the local organic products and to post their ideas on how to improve the management of the agricultural park.

	<p>86 people answered the questionnaire and 56 uploaded posts, videos, etc. A bicycle was the award for the participants in this dialogue. The feedback exceeded the expectations of the Municipality. A report with all the ideas gathered is being analyzed by the Consortium of Gallecs in order to be presented to the political representatives of the Board of the Consortium. The report will also be sent to the participants of the dialogue, who will be invited to attend a public meeting with the manager of Gallecs Consortium. During the meeting outcomes of the evaluation of the ideas will be presented.</p> <p>Mollet del Valles Municipality is very satisfied with the results of this dialogue, both in terms of number of users and quality of the posts. During the internal evaluation, the Municipality realized that they could have allocated human resources to give feedback to users posts during the implementation of the dialogue. Additionally, feedback should have been managed faster (report, meetings, etc) but as Gallecs Consortium includes 6 municipalities and the Catalan Government the process is quite slow.</p>
<p>Mollet blossomed Village (this is the name of an award for the excellent maintenance of the parks in the city)</p>	<p>The purpose of this dialogue was the Mollet del Valles Municipality to find out if they had effectively disseminated the award they recently received for the maintenance of Mollet parks. Additionally, citizens were invited to share posts, pictures and videos of their favorite parks of the city. 32 citizens answered the questionnaire and 30 posts, videos, etc were uploaded on the platform. According to the results of the questionnaire, more than 60% were aware of the award. The feedback was not the expected one. This dialogue opened at the same time with the dialogue about the agricultural park of Gallecs. It was noticed that most of the posts could have fitted in the other dialogue as well, so perhaps there was confusion in citizens' perception on these dialogues.</p> <p>The Municipality will take into consideration the results of this dialogue when releasing a catalogue for protected trees.</p>
<p>Urban garden of Can Borrell</p> <p><u>Background information on the dialogue:</u> In 2016, the Civic Center of Can Borrell launched a project to build an urban vertical garden with pallets outside the main entrance of the center. This year, the main goal is the engagement of the neighbors of Can Borrell in taking care of the garden and promoting values such as environmental awareness and citizenship engagement.</p> <p>The project is very successful so far</p>	<p>113 people have answered the questionnaire and 89 assessed the initiative as very interesting and affirmed that Mollet should replicate this initiative across the city.</p> <p>There have been 95 posts, most of them from young people. Most of them have uploaded photos taking care of the garden.</p> <p>Following this dialogue, the results will be shared with the following municipal departments that are currently active in the project management:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cultural department - Environmental department - Education department <p>A meeting with the respective politicians will be arranged in order to present the outputs of the dialogue and take decisions on the</p>

<p>and the coordinators of the civic centre, in charge of the project, were willing to create this dialogue in order to get the feedback of current users before taking the initiative to expand the vertical urban garden of Can Borrell and deciding to create new ones in other neighbourhoods of Mollet.</p>	<p>expansion of the urban gardens within the city and on the new city regulation for urban gardens.</p> <p>Additionally, a report with the main outputs will be sent to all participants.</p> <p>This dialogue was promoted through a comprehensive campaign, while an award, an urban garden kit to place in balconies or terraces, was given to the participants after a drawn.</p>
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When the Municipality started the implementation of the pilot, decided to launch two appealing parallel dialogues with attractive awards that were not planned in an earlier stage:

- Gallecs, your park. Come and enjoy it!
- Mollet blossomed village

This was a part of strategy to attract more young citizens and engage them in decision making concerning local environmental issues. As it can be noticed in the table above, the most attractive dialogue is the “Urban garden of Can Borrell” with 113 participants and 95 posts.

Initial Pilot Plan & Upcoming Dialogues:

Mollet del Valles Municipality has second thoughts about the implementation of the three dialogues below that were initially planned.

- Weekly outdoor market: it would be more interesting to run dialogues connected to energy efficiency or mobility
- Round table with policy makers: although this dialogue was initially planned the Municipality believes that they should find a more strategic way of launching it.
- “Summer city Festival challenge”: Mollet Municipality had several meetings with the two cultural associations that coordinate the Summer Festival and finally Municipality’s proposal on the organization of the festival was not accepted. The argument is that they already have too many challenges and few resources to manage them.

Additionally, the Municipality decided to create several dialogues that were not initially planned and is currently discussing the creation of a dialogue that will invite citizens to use the platform and evaluate Municipality’s public services. Another dialogue on the Local Plan for waste prevention is also being discussed to be uploaded on the platform.

The dialogues that will be launched after the summer are the following ones:

- More pedestrian streets
- Food policy at local level
- Artisan’s fair quiz on local and organic products
- Nature itineraries

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Initial pilot plan with the environmental issues proposed to be brought in the STEP platform									
Project months	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29
Environmental issues									
<i>City plan for young people</i>									
<i>Round table with policy-makers</i>									
<i>Weekly outdoor market</i>									
<i>City environmental volunteers: Green Ambassadors</i>									
<i>Nature itineraries</i>									
<i>More pedestrian streets?</i>									
<i>STEP as a tool for education</i>									
<i>Urban gardening</i>									
<i>Food policy at local level</i>									
<i>Summer city festival challenge</i>									
<i>Artizan's fair quiz on local and organic products</i>									

Updated Pilot Plan						
Project months	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29
Environmental issues						
<i>Food policy at local level</i>						
<i>Artizan's fair quiz on local and organic products</i>						
<i>More pedestrian streets</i>						
<i>Nature itineraries</i>						

Inclusion

The dialogue "Urban Garden" of Can Borrell has been a perfect example on how to engage young people with fewer opportunities. Most of the participants of the dialogue attend free IT classes and had the opportunity to get involved in the project during the classes. Furthermore, there are many young who refer to the civic centers in order to use the free wifi connections. In this context, they are being informed about the STEP project and they are being invited to participate in the dialogues.

2.1.3. Valdemoro Municipality

Valdemoro Municipality has implemented a number of dissemination activities with a special focus on schools and high school students. One of the Municipality's basic goals is to inspire behavioral change to this target group and to engage them to participate in decision making from a very early stage.

Dialogues at STEP platform					
Issue	Scenario	Type	Start	End	No of participants
Let's take care of our parks	Call for ideas	Public	18/1/2017	31/08/2017	26
Recycle Valdemoro	Call for ideas	Public	28/12/2016	31/3/2017	18
Ideas for a new cycling route in Valdemoro	Call for ideas	Public	28/12/2016	31/03/2017	30
Urban gardens; Responsible and healthy cultivation	E-petition	Public	15/05/2017	31/07/2017	6
Keeping the streets clean from dog excrement	Call for ideas	Public	15/05/2017	30/09/2017	5

The Municipality of Valdemoro has uploaded 5 dialogues on the STEP platform so far and the dialogue that has attracted most the interest of citizens is the one about the new cycling route in Valdemoro. However, the number of participants is currently lower than expected. Many people were reached through events, activities and workshops but the participation in the platform is low. All the dissemination tools of the City Council and the STEP platform for the promotion of the dialogues were used. Young people would be interested in using a new platform or app, but it should be well-known and be used by their inner cycle.

In order to tackle this issue, the Municipality of Valdemoro decided to intensify the dissemination activities for the promotion of the STEP platform to young users. Additionally, Valdemoro's action plan includes:

- Mentoring system:

Valdemoro will implement a mentoring system where a team of educators will train youth groups to register and spread the platform to other groups. These young people will teach other youngsters how to use the platform and encourage them to register in it.

- More involvement of stakeholders:

The Valdemoro Municipality will contact stakeholders directly linked to the topic of each dialogue and create synergies with them, so as to promote the dialogues involve young volunteers.

- Contest:

A competition that will include a prize will be set up to promote the participation of young people in the STEP platform.

Moreover, in order to reach a greater number of young people the Municipality is in close cooperation with the Department of Prevention (Council of Social Affairs and Inequality).

Until the end of May, one dialogue was concluded in Valdemoro’s pilot and is presented in the following table.

Dialogue	Brief Description
Recycle Valdemoro	The participants in this dialogue were 18 in total. The main purpose of this dialogue was to motivate citizens to share their opinion on how to reduce waste in the city. According to the feedback received, citizens are aware of recycling methods and sensitized on the environment. The results of this dialogue were further discussed with the core team, in order to be sent to representatives of schools and politicians. The representatives of schools will get the results and the ideas of the dialogue and share them with students and youth group through informative talks. Politicians will take action through recycle campaigns.

Initial Pilot Plan & Upcoming Dialogues:

Following the launching of the first dialogues on the STEP platform and after noticing the results of young citizens’ participation the Municipality of Valdemoro decided to update the initial plan of dialogues in order to make it more attractive to young users. Both plans are presented below. Additionally, the Municipality decided to merge the dialogues “Consult young citizens on the reforestation of the parks with tree species from a list proposed by the Valdemoro Municipality” and “Make a voluntary call to collect the waste accumulated in the banks of the "La cañada" stream”in the dialogue: "Ask where to locate new green spaces and park areas in Valdemoro City".

Initial pilot plan with the environmental issues proposed to be brought in the STEP platform									
Project months	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29
Environmental issues									
Consult young citizens on water savings, combined with the development of a water treatment plant.									
Ask where to locate new green spaces and park areas in the Valdemoro city									
Inform and consult young citizens on the Urban Development Plan.									
Present how the collection of dog excrement on the streets works and consult young people on new ideas for collection.									
Reforest the parks with tree species from a list consulting proposed by the municipality.									
Ask young citizens to reorganize the urban transport network by giving them the chance to place bus stops.									

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Ask young people where to place garbage collection bins in buildings and public spaces.									
Make a voluntary call to collect the waste accumulated in the margins of the "La cañada" stream.									
Ask young people where to build a path for bike lane in Valdemoro city.									

Updated Pilot Plan						
Project months	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29
Environmental issues						
Ask young people where to place garbage collection bins in buildings and public spaces.						
Ask where to locate new green spaces and park areas in the Valdemoro city						
Ask young people where to build a path for bike lane in Valdemoro city.						
Present how the collection of dog excrement on the streets works and consult young people on new ideas for collection.						
Request for more urban orchards; cultivate our healthy foods						
Request to young people of images that represent their environmental concerns						
Consult young citizens on water savings, combined with the development of a water treatment plant.						
Ask young citizens to reorganize the urban transport network by giving them the chance to place bus stops						

Inclusion

Valdemoro's pilot plan has included initiatives focused on groups of disabled citizens and people at social risk, giving them the opportunity to participate in STEP events and activities, as well as participate in STEP platform dialogues. To achieve this, the Municipality had meetings with persons in charge of these groups and formed a specific action plan. Additionally, meetings with the members of the youth groups took place in order to present the platform, the dialogues and to invite them to participate.

2.1.4 Hatay Metropolitan Municipality

Until the end of May, the Municipality of Hatay had uploaded 4 dialogues on the STEP platform, which are presented at the table below.

Dialogues at STEP platform					
Issue	Scenario	Type	Start	End	No of participants
Priority Green for Hatay	Call for ideas	Public	3/3/2017	10/09/2017	209
Let's uncover Hatay's environmental beauties!!!!	Call for ideas	Public	20/03/2017	15/05/2017	432
Young create their own parks...	Consultant	Public	31/03/2017	30/06/2017	77
EXPO 2021 Hatay... Share your ideas	Call for ideas	Public	2/05/2017	10/10/2017	106

As it can be seen in the table above, Hatay's most popular dialogue is the one under the title: "Let's uncover Hatay's environmental beauties!!!", with 432 participants. This dialogue was concluded in May and is further elaborated at the table below. The dialogue "Priority Green for Hatay" is the second most popular one with 209 participants. The high number of participants is a result of Hatay's intensive communication and dissemination strategy, which focused in engaging young people in the STEP platform using dialogues that would attract their interest.

Dialogue	Brief Description
Let's uncover the environmental beauties of Hatay...!!	The main goal of this dialogue was to introduce the platform to young citizens and engage them in the STEP solution. In this context, the Municipality of Hatay invited young citizens to upload on the platform photos that will present beautiful natural sceneries, green spots and areas of the Municipality, etc. 432 young citizens participated in the dialogue and uploaded relevant material. The Municipality of Hatay will use these photos in order to create a collage that will be uploaded in Hatay's main page of the platform.

Initial Pilot Plan & Upcoming Dialogues:

The Municipality of Hatay follows the initial plan and makes necessary additions according to the needs that arise. Prior to the creation of the dialogue "Establishing a masterplan for an aromatic and medicinal plant park", the Municipality has to establish an Institution for the development of the city's ecological masterplan (Eco City Agency). The first steps have been made, but due to financial issues the Agency will need another one year in order to be fully established, so the creation of the aforementioned dialogue will be affected and perhaps will be cancelled.

Moreover, the Municipality of Hatay intends to bring under public participation the issues below:

- Bicycle road planning. The Municipality will ask young people to create their own bike route and then will present the results of the dialogue to the relevant municipality department in order to take them into account in their future schedule. An award is foreseen for the best suggestions of this dialogue.
- Asi river cleaning concepts: The Municipality will ask citizens to provide ideas on the topic and will forward the results to the respective municipality department.

Initial pilot plan with the environmental issues proposed to be brought in the STEP platform									
Project months	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29
Environmental issues									
<i>Round table with policy-makers</i>									
<i>Round table with environmental experts and NGO's</i>									
<i>Priority for Green Hatay</i>									
<i>Establishing a masterplan for an aromatic and medicinal plant park</i>									
<i>Urban gardening selection</i>									

Updated Pilot Plan						
Project months	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29
Environmental issues						
<i>Bicycle road planning</i>						
<i>Asi river cleaning concepts</i>						

Inclusion:

Until October 2017, the Municipality we set info kiosks central areas of the city. At least one person from the STEP team will be at the stand, which will be equipped with 4 tablets and an independent internet access. People with no access to the internet will be able to be informed for the STEP dialogues and participate in them through these info kiosks. The info kiosks will be set at the city center, shopping centers, universities, events and places which are mostly visited by the young people.

2.1.5 Association of the Communities of Locride area

The Association of the Communities of Locride area has uploaded 5 dialogues in the STEP platform so far. However, due to internal issues in the Association, the pilot was not implemented as it was expected. The internal issues were mainly the lengthy administrative procedures for the approval of the municipality budget, resulting in delayed payments to contracted personnel. As a result, the level of participation in the Locride pilot is still low. However, this problem was resolved in May, and it is expected that by launching new dialogues and intensifying the pilot promotion activities it will be possible to reach the targets at the end of the project. Additionally, the Association decided to extend the deadline of the uploaded dialogues in order to collect more feedback from young users. The table below presents the dialogues that have been uploaded on the STEP platform until the end of May 2017. There are no concluded dialogues in this pilot so far.

It should be noted that through the activities of the STEP team in Calabria, the Municipality of Sant'Agata del Bianco, which is located within the metropolitan city of Reggio Calabria, has amended its municipal statute in order to allow the implementation of e-petitions through the STEP platform. Moreover, with this amendment young citizens above 16 years old have the right to submit e-petitions.

The changes referred to art. 34 of Sant'Agata del Bianco Statute and were officially agreed during the Municipal Council meeting, which was held in 28th of April 2017. Following this amendment, Sant'Agata is the first Calabrian municipality that allows young people above the age of 16 to initiate electronic petitions. In addition, the number of requested signatures in a petition, which will oblige the administration to evaluate the proposal, has been reduced to fifty. This amendment was an important step for spreading new forms of digital democracy to young people in the southernmost region of Italy.

Dialogues at STEP platform					
Issue	Scenario	Type	Start	End	No of participants
Waste water treatment: Keep the sea clean in Locride Area	Call for ideas	Public	3/05/2017	31/08/2017	21
Recycling in Locride area	Call for ideas and e-petitions	Public	2/02/2017	31/08/2017	20
New green areas in the Locride	Call for ideas and e-petitions	Public	23/03/2017	31/08/2017	22
Separate collection of waste and recycling: no waste landfills	Call for ideas & E-petitions	Public	3/05/2017	31/08/2017	7
Ring road in the city of Siderno	Call for ideas and e-petitions	Public	3/05/2017	31/08/2017	32

Initial Pilot Plan & Upcoming Dialogues:

The Association of the Communities of Locride area decided to update the initial plan of dialogues and bring under public participation additional local issues that need to be tackled. In this context, within the following months two more dialogues are planned to be uploaded on the STEP platform:

- Promote the consumption of water coming from springs.
- New project for Urban Green Park in Sant'Ilario dello Jonio

Furthermore, the Association of the Communities of Locride area discusses additional issues that could be brought under public participation through the STEP platform.

Initial pilot plan with the environmental issues proposed to be brought in the STEP platform										
Project months	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29
Environmental issues										
<i>Proposal for waste collection door to door against the current road containers waste collection</i>										
<i>New ideas to introduce waste sorting at work, in schools, in public spaces</i>										
<i>Select location for new green and park areas in the cities</i>										
<i>Proposal for green water treatment plant</i>										

Updated pilot plan						
Project months	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29
Environmental issues						
<i>Promote the consumption of water coming from springs.</i>						
<i>New project for Urban Green Park in Sant’Ilario dello Jonio</i>						

2.1.6 Resilient Thessaloniki

The additional pilot of Thessaloniki that joined STEP on its own accord rescheduled the local pilot plan, so as the first dialogues would be uploaded onto the STEP platform at the beginning of June.

The reason of this reschedule is because Rockefeller Foundation selected Resilient Thessaloniki to be granted with the “Street Plans” services. Street Plans is an award-winning urban planning, design, and research/advocacy firm located in America. This is a very well-known firm for advancing innovative practices to test and implement projects on different topics including open streets and public space stewardship. One of the main priorities of the Municipality’s administration is to enhance active citizen participation, empower self-organizing and support new forms of collective action to address issues of public concern. The Municipality of Thessaloniki wants to enable citizens to interfere and embellish urban spaces in their neighborhood. Street Plans will translate this initiative into a strategic plan and a legal framework that will describe the process for the evaluation of citizens’ proposals. Additionally, the STEP tool will be used by the Municipality for this initiative.

In April 2017, Resilient Thessaloniki organized a workshop to present the STEP platform and the Street Plans’ project to young citizens of Thessaloniki. During this workshop a visit at Mina’s Patrikiou park was organized and the participants were asked to provide ideas for interventions in the broader area. All the collected ideas

were grouped in three categories and the Municipality of Thessaloniki will use the STEP platform to bring these ideas under public consultation. The first dialogues of Thessaloniki's pilot are expected to be uploaded at the beginning of June.

2.2 EU Pilot

Since the beginning of February 2017, the STEP platform is being pilot tested at local level by STEP pilot partners. In the meantime, the consortium agreed on fully exploiting the platform and use it at Pan-European level, in the framework of a general European pilot test, which will invite young people to voice their opinions on general issues concerning the environment.

In this framework, DRAXIS and YEE have set up the first EU dialogue, which is going to go public in July 2017. The topic of the first EU dialogue is about the 17 Global Sustainable Development Goals (SDG's) and the title of the dialogue is: "17 Global Sustainable Development Goals. Which are more important to you?". The purpose of this dialogue is to ask from young European citizens to choose 5 out of the 17 SDG's and highlight the 5 most important according to their opinion. Through this dialogue European youngsters will be informed about the importance of the 17 SDG's and will create the European SDG Youth List. Once the dialogue is concluded a report will be conducted and sent to the respective UNDP department and to the EU.

Additional dialogues will be brought to the STEP platform by the YEE and DRAXIS within the next months.

Moreover, the STEP team seeks for collaboration with Environmental NGOs and other Agencies that could possibly use the platform in order to create a timeline, a questionnaire, or initiate an e-petition and ask from young European citizens to share their opinions on specific environmental topics. Various meetings have already taken place in the previous months and they are resented below.

Meeting with the Chairwoman of the ENVI Committee of the European Parliament

Based on this plan, the STEP team has already had two meetings with Mrs Adina-Ioana VĂLEAN, Chairwoman of the [Environment, Public Health and Food Safety Committee](#) of the European Parliament (ENVI Committee). Both meetings took place at the offices of the ENVI Committee, at the European Parliament. During the meetings the STEP team presented the project and the platform focusing specifically on the social media monitoring tool and the timeline, two basic features that could be instantly used by the ENVI Committee. Additionally, it was noted that the STEP platform could be used by the ENVI Committee as a unique tool that not only would raise youth awareness on the environmental issues the ENVI Committee is in charge of, but would also foster young people's empowerment and active participation in democratic life. The feedback received by Mrs Valean was very positive and she pointed out that the graphic identity of the platform is quite user friendly and welcoming for young users. Mrs Valean volunteered to introduce the STEP Platform to the members of the ENVI Committee and to investigate possible ways of collaboration.

Meeting with BRAL

Citizens Action Brussels (BRAL) is a city movement striving to make Brussels sustainable and build an environmentally friendly, affordable and solidary city. BRAL organises actions, lobbying groups, supports citizens' initiatives and provides advice to the authorities. The STEP team met the representatives of BRAL at their offices in Brussels and presented the STEP platform to them. Discussions followed on how they could support the dissemination of the tool and how they could use it in order to interact with citizens on atmospheric pollution issues and create related dialogues. It was agreed to organize an online presentation in order to demonstrate the STEP platform to additional members of BRAL.

2.3 Monitoring and control

The monitoring of the work progress is a key process for the successful implementation of the STEP project, since it keeps the STEP team alerted and allows tracing any risks, rescheduling and planning additional future activities. DRAXIS is responsible for the monitoring of the STEP pilots. A comprehensive plan was created for the monitoring of the STEP pilots. In order to ensure the timely and smooth implementation of the pilots operation, from Month 17 (October 2016), all pilot partners were receiving a monthly plan with the actions they had to carry out. Additional online meetings were/are taking place between DRAXIS and each pilot partner every month in order to monitor the progress, agree on the action plan of the following month and discuss any problems encountered. The overall progress of the pilots is monitored according to the impact indicators which have been set in the DoA, and are presented in the table below.

Indicator of success	Measurement technique	Target achieved until the end of May 2017	Target value ¹
Demonstration, Validation and Usability			
Number of young people involved in pilot	Demonstration in 4 pilot countries	Italy: 299 Spain: 1,173 Greece: 586 Turkey: 1,792	Italy: 1,500 Spain: 1,200 Greece: 3,000 Turkey: 3,500 TOTAL: 8,200
Number of policy makers involved in pilot	Demonstration in 4 pilot countries	Italy: 12 Spain: 10 Greece: 13 Turkey: 20	Italy: 20 Spain: 20 Greece: 20 Turkey: 25 TOTAL: 85
Number of decision-making procedures piloted through STEP	Demonstration in 4 pilot countries	Italy: 5 Spain: 12 Greece: 23 Turkey: 4	Italy: 15 Spain: 15 Greece: 15 Turkey: 20 TOTAL: 65
Number of downloads of STEP app	Demonstration in 4 pilot countries	Italy: 116 Spain: 93 Greece: 31 Turkey: 242	Italy: 1,000 Spain: 1,000 Greece: 2,000 Turkey: 2,500 TOTAL: 6,500
Legal and Ethical Compliance	Based on a detailed ethical and legal review, all relevant national and European level requirements are met, enabling the solution to be delivered competitively across the EU and participating countries.	0 complaints so far	All pilots should comply with the ethical guidelines in this sector. Minimum amount of complaints (less than 1% among the service's users) should be expressed.
Sustainability and Awareness			
Number of additional public authorities interested in adopting STEP	Demonstration in 4 pilot countries	Italy: 3 Spain: 2 Greece: 2	Italy: 2 Spain: 2 Greece: 2

¹ The target value estimations are based on the assumption that 20% of the population of young people of the pilot locations will be reached through the STEP dissemination activities, and that approximately 2 – 5% of these will actually use the STEP platform.

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		Turkey: -	Turkey: 2 TOTAL: 8
Number of young people informed about STEP	Demonstration in 4 pilot countries	Italy: 2,478 Spain: 5.540 Greece: 2.900 Turkey: 9,520	Italy: 4,500 Spain: 3,500 Greece: 19,000 Turkey: 35,000 TOTAL: 62,000
Number of young people informed about STEP beyond the pilot area	Demonstration in 4 pilot countries 5% of the national youth population 18-29		Italy: 350.000 Spain: 300.000 Greece: 50.000 Turkey: 500.000 TOTAL: 1.200.000

As one notices in the table above, some of the pilots are performing quite well in terms of young people involved in pilot, number of policy makers involved in pilot and number of decision-making procedures piloted through STEP. Some of the targets have already been achieved in some pilot areas and some others are about to be achieved within the following months. However, the pilot of Crete and Locride should put extra effort in order to attract additional young users and involve them in the pilots. A number of additional dissemination activities presented in D7.5 2nd Report of Dissemination Activities and dialogues that were presented in the updated pilot plans of the present deliverable have been scheduled for the following months.

Additionally, all partners should put extra effort in order to increase the number of downloads of the STEP app, which is quite low. As the pilot partners have reported, one of the main obstacles is the slow wi-fi connection in the areas and the spaces that the dissemination activities take place. However, in order to tackle this problem, a new strategy has been developed. The pilot partners will organize contests, which will be promoted through the events they will organize/participate in, as well as through their social media accounts. The awards of these contests will be different in each pilot area. Additionally, as it was discussed in the previous project meeting that took place in Italy at the end of May, the partners will allocate an amount that will cover the traveling expenses of 5 young users, who will download the STEP app (one per pilot area) in order to participate at projects' final conference. This target will be monitored very carefully and additional actions will take place in case it's needed.

As for the "Legal and Ethical Compliance" target, so far the STEP team has not received any complaints. Information about this indicator could be found in D 2.3 Guidelines for handling ethical, legal issues, and data protection.

A number of meetings have already taken place for effective dissemination and full valorisation of the STEP solution. The STEP partners have organised meetings with representatives of local authorities. As it has been indicated the Municipality of Thessaloniki decided to join the STEP pilots and use the solution for enhancing youth e-participation.

The indicator "Number of young people informed about STEP" derives by the reports about the dissemination activities that each pilot submits at the end of each month.

Finally, as far as the indicator "Number of young people informed about STEP beyond the pilot area", is concerned, since it is impossible to know the exact number of young people that have been informed about STEP beyond the pilot area, the partners will calculate this number at the end of the project based on estimations. More particularly, each pilot partner will select one, or two, TV channels /radio stations / shows /magazines, etc with mass appeal to young ages, or prime time zones in order to broadcast the STEP video, give interviews, make advertisements, etc. Based on the reach of these activities, this number will be calculated for each pilot individually according to the audience (%of young people) and the special characteristics of each mass media mean.

2.4 Usage Data from the Platform

Table 2.1 Number of Users / Dialogues, Posts & Questionnaire response for each of the STEP Pilots (taken July 7th 2017)

	Total Users Count	Dialogues / Challenges Count	Unique Count (made by users)	Posts (made by)	Questionnaire responses
Crete	585	23	57		506
Hatay	2060	10	918		482
Locride	317	8	96		0
Mollet	1510	12	279		6797
Thessaloniki	62	8	50*		13**
Valdemoro	157	6	74		92

The table above shows the number of STEP users along with the number of Dialogues (Challenges) that have been released by the Pilots. To calculate the number of posts made the usage data was exported to excel from the STEP advanced admin page, the data was then sorted to by 'posts' and any made by the web crawler (Crawley Green) were removed before the number was calculated.

The large differences in the number of posts made is in part a reflection of the types of Dialogues released, for example Call for Ideas dialogues results in a much larger number of unique posts by young people, whereas the Environmental Consultation or Call for petitions often involved users completing a short survey instead of making posts, thus number of posts is lower per user (eg in Crete) where the dialogues are mainly of this type. The table shows the number of questionnaires answered, allowing a better understanding of how the platform is being used and More details on the actions made for each Dialogue are presented below in section 2.2 Status of STEP pilots

* 48 of these made by resilient Thessaloniki ** These 13 all made by admin accounts/ POs.

2.5 Survey Results

In order to evaluate the opinion of both young people and Policy Makers/Public officers we devised surveys to enable some quantitative data to be gathered using likert scale questions in addition to open ended questions to allow for more detailed responses. The surveys that have been distributed to young people taking part in the Dialogues corresponded to the type of eParticipation process that people took part in. These related to the 'Call for Ideas', 'Environmental Consultation Process' and 'Call for Petitions' Dialogues that had been put forward at this stage. The link to the Google Forms survey was emailed to participants towards the end of the Dialogue life span.

Below we present some of the preliminary findings from the survey results. As has already been discussed, numbers of responses at this point are low due to lower than anticipated participation levels and the difficulties of getting young people to take the time to fill in a survey. All the Pilot partners are working hard to address this issue and we also plan to change the way the survey is distributed, moving to a survey that can be completed within the STEP platform. For the 'Call for Ideas' surveys we have combined the results from Young European Citizens from four of the Pilots to present a more accurate overall view of Young People's opinion and experience with the platform. For the other processes we have presented individual Pilot responses. In addition to the Young People Surveys, Policy Maker surveys were also sent to the relevant people involved in the STEP pilot dialogues. We have also ensured that at least one Policy Maker from each Pilot was interviewed to gain more in depth feedback of their experience and to understand any issues they have encountered to date with the platform.

Table 2.1 showing numbers of People responding to the Survey Requests (For all the Dialogue Types)

Survey Respondents	Young People	Public Officers	Total
Mollet	6	1	7
Valdemoro	7	4	11
Crete	9 *(8 reported)	5	14
Hatay	19 (17 reported)	8	27
Locride / Calabria	0	12	12

* A very small number of surveys were completed after the data had been analysed and reported.

2.5.1 Young European Citizen (YEC) Surveys

2.5.1.1 Crete Environmental Consultation Process:

Of the 3 people who responded to this survey after participating in an Environmental Consultation Process Dialogue, one person was a student and two full time employed, all were male.

When asked if they had enough time to consider and submit their issues two people agreed and one strongly agreed (**Positive**). When asked about the interest in viewing comments submitted by others, one person was neutral, one agreed and the other strongly agreed (**Positive**).

For ease of use 2 people agreed and one strongly agreed that the platform was easy to use (**Positive**); all 3 people agreed that the platform was attractive (**Positive**), and one person agreed that it was fun to use whilst the other 2 remained neutral (**Neutral**).

Help features: two people agreed that the help features were useful, whilst the other said it was not applicable (ie hadn't used them) (**Positive**). For the level of support available, one person remained neutral (perhaps not used it) whilst one agreed and one strongly agreed that there was a sufficient level of support if a problem was encountered (**Positive**).

For the question (Q7) on how effective the STEP platform was in

- i) Seeing what ideas other young people are posting on environmental issues
one person was neutral, one agreed and one strongly agreed (**Positive**).
- ii) Voicing their concerns to the relevant policy makers
All 3 people agreed (one strongly) (**Positive**).
- iii) Getting other YP interested in important environmental issues
one person agreed, whilst 2 strongly agreed. (**Positive**).

For question 8 – were the **comments/recommendations made of high quality**, then 2 people were neutral whilst one person agreed. (**Neutral**)

For question 9 – asking about **trust** levels after using the platform then one person disagreed, one was neutral and one agreed. (**Neutral**)

For question 10 asking if the comments on the **feedback** on how the results of the consultation process had been exploited were sufficient then one person disagreed and the other two were neutral. (**Negative** – but perhaps too early at this stage)

Question 11 asked if STEP is likely to **increase the number of young people** who will share their concerns with local authorities during a consultation process, two people were neutral whilst one agreed that it would. (**Slightly Positive**).

Question 12 asked if the participant would **recommend the platform** to other young people; two people strongly agreed whilst one disagreed (**Slightly Positive**).

Q13 Is there anything that would **stop you from using the platform again**?

“To disregard citizens' views on an environmental issue in the process of evaluating the study through the administration. “Essentially, the platform should in fact prove its importance.” “Needs improvement” “No”.

2.5.1.2 Valdemoro Environmental Consultation Process:

Of the 6 young people who responded to the survey in May after participating in an Environmental Consultation Dialogue, half (3) were part-time students and half full-time students.

The first part of question 4 asked if they were confident about submitting comments regarding the consultation; two people disagreed, three agreed and one strongly agreed. Overall 66% positive 33% negative (**Slightly Positive**).

Everyone agreed or strongly agreed with the second question, asking if they had **enough time to consider the issues (Positive)**; the third question asked about **interest in seeing other comments** that were submitted, where one person was neutral and the other 5 agreed (4) or strongly agreed (1) that they were interested (**Positive**).

For question 5, 2 participants (33%) stated that they disagreed that the platform was **intuitive** to use, the remaining 66% either agreed (50%) or strongly agreed (17%) that it was intuitive. (**Neutral/Slightly Positive**)

The majority (5/6) participants agreed that the platform was **attractive**, with just one remaining neutral (**Positive**).

The response to **ease of use** was very mixed, with one person strongly disagreeing and one disagreeing that the platform was easy to use, one remained neutral, two people agreed and one strongly agreed with the statement. (**Neutral**). Three participants agreed that the **help features** were useful, the other 3 had not used them (**Positive**). When asked if the level of **support** was good when encountering a problem, 2 were neutral and one person said it wasn't applicable as they hadn't used this feature (**Neutral**).

Question 7 asks if the platform was effective in:

- a) **Viewing the suggestions** other young people had submitted regarding the environment
- b) **Voicing views / concerns** to the relevant policy makers
- c) **Raising awareness** of important environmental issues with peers

Responses to these questions was **Positive**, all participants agreeing /strongly agreeing that the platform was effective (only one neutral for the raising awareness question).

Question 8 asked if the suggestions made by young people to the platform were of high quality; 1 person was neutral, 3 agreed and 1 strongly agreed (**Positive**).

Question 9 asked if YP were more able to **trust** local policy makers after using the platform, the responses here were mixed, 3 people were neutral 2 agreed and one strongly disagreed (**Neutral**).

Question 10 asked if the **feedback given** on how the YP comments had been taken into consideration, 3 people were neutral and 3 agreed. (**Slightly Positive**) We should bear in mind here that at this early stage it is a little early for the Pilots to have responded in some cases.

Question 11 asked if the STEP platform would be likely to **increase the number of YP participating** in the consultation process. Response to this was very positive with all YP agreeing (4) or strongly agreeing (2) (**Positive**).

Q12 asked if they would **recommend** the platform to other YP to participate in a consultation process; 1 person was neutral, 1 agreed and 3 agreed (**Positive**).

Q13 asked if there was anything that would **prevent the use of the STEP** platform; the following free text answers were given: "There is nothing that prevents using STEP" ; "There was no problem" "Nothing" "No" (**Positive**), with one more critical response - " I find it **hard to use** the application, it needs to be **more visual**, and therefore I did not use it too much" (**Negative**). Other free text comments received were:

"They had to help me find the name of the projects, since they are **not seen** with the naked eye, nor is there an index. It would be good if that **first page was more intuitive** and everything was clearly seen. I would also give the **option to choose the language**." "A link to connect to more visible social networks"

"I think that the format of social network that step has is insufficient and very lousy at the time of its use"

Additional Comments: "I liked reading the comments and seeing how other young people think and what they propose to change things"

Only one YEC from Valdemoro responded to the survey request for the Call for Ideas Dialogue – the results from this have been included in the summary in section 2.1.5 (Summary of Call for Ideas – YECs).

2.5.1.3. Hatay Call for Petitions YECs

Of the 10 responses received from this survey after participating in a Call for Petitions Dialogue, all were full-time students; 90% aged 21-24 10% 16-20 90% female 10% male

Question 4 Taking Part: One person strongly disagreed and 2 disagreed about being confident about how to submit their petition 2 people were neutral, 1 agreed and 4 strongly agreed that they were confident.

Neutral

When asked about having enough time to consider the issues then 2 people were neutral, 5 agreed and 2 strongly agreed that they had enough time. Just 1 person strongly disagreed with this statement.

Slightly Positive

Regarding being **interested in viewing the other petitions** people were submitting, 3 people were neutral, 3 people agreed, 2 strongly agreed that they were interested. 1 person disagreed and 1 strongly disagreed.

Neutral / Slightly Positive

Q5 Ease of Use /enjoyable : 7 people agreed that the platform was **intuitive** to use, with 3 people neutral.

Positive

8 people agreed and 1 strongly agreed that it was **easy to use** (sympathetic) with 1 neutral. **Positive**

1 person strongly disagreed, 2 people were neutral, 3 agreed and 4 strongly agreed that it was **enjoyable to use**. **Slightly Positive**

Q6 Help features: 2 people were neutral about help features being useful, 4 agreed and 4 strongly agreed that the help features were useful. **Positive**

When asked if the level of support was good when encountering a problem, 1 person was neutral, 4 agreed, and 4 strongly agreed. One person said it wasn't applicable as they hadn't used the features. **Positive**

For the question (Q7) on how effective the STEP platform was in

i) Seeing what ideas other young people are posting on environmental issues

3 people were neutral, 5 people agreed and 2 strongly agreed. **Positive**

ii) Voicing their concerns to the relevant policy makers

1 person neutral, 8 people agreed and 1 strongly agreed. **Very Positive**

iii) Getting other YP interested in important environmental issues

1 person neutral, 3 agreed and 6 strongly agreed. **Very Positive**

Question 8 asked if the **contributions** made to the STEP platform were **of high quality**; 1 person was neutral, 1 disagreed, 5 people agreed and 3 strongly agreed. **Positive**

Question 9 asked if after using STEP did the YP feel more able to **trust** local policy makers; responses to this question were quite positive – 5 people agreed, 3 strongly agreed and 3 were neutral. **Positive**

Question 10 asked if the **feedback** given regarding how the YP contributions have been considered was adequate; 1 disagreed, 5 people were neutral, 3 agreed and 1 strongly agreed. **Neutral**

Responses to the question (11) on if the platform is likely to **increase the number of YP** sharing ideas /petitions with the local municipality, then 2 people were neutral, 1 agreed and 7 strongly agreed. **Positive**

Responses to the question (12) on if the YP would **recommend** the STEP platform to others, then 1 person disagreed, 1 was neutral one agreed and the other 7 people strongly agreed. **Positive**

No comments given in the free text questions.

2.5.1.4 Summary Combined YEC Survey Responses (Call for Ideas)

As the numbers of survey responses for the individual Pilot dialogues was low, here we combine the total responses for the 'Call for Ideas' survey to give a more general overview of what Young European Citizens think about the platform at this stage (total of 19 responses). This survey was distributed to those young people participating in a 'Call for Ideas' dialogue. This combined data came from Crete (5 responses), Mollet (6 responses), Hatay (7 responses) & Valdemoro (1 response).

Fig 2.0 Combined Survey data showing young people's confidence for submitting ideas to the STEP platform

The percentage of people confident about submitting ideas to the platform was 58% (16% agree & 42% strongly agree), 32% neutral and 11% not confident. Although there are a high number of people strongly agreeing, the fact that there are people who are unsure of how to submit ideas to the platform means that further work (usability testing) will need to be done to ensure that these values improve and a larger number of users are confident.

Fig 2.1 Combined Survey data showing young people's opinion on how engaging the STEP platform is

73% agreed that the platform was engaging with 16% neutral and 11% disagreeing.

This is a fairly positive result and only 11% thought that the platform was not engaging, although efforts will be made to improve this score by considering the gamification aspects.

Fig 2.3 Combined Survey data showing young people's opinion of how enjoyable the STEP platform is to use

78% agreed or strongly agreed that the platform was enjoyable to use with 11% neutral and 11% disagreeing. This result is positive and we feel the result reflects well on the platform.

Fig 2.4 Combined Survey data showing how effective young people consider STEP to be for voicing their opinion to the relevant person

A very positive response was given for how effective the platform was in voicing their concerns to the relevant person, with a total of 84% agreeing and only 16% remaining neutral on this point.

Fig 2.5 Combined Survey data showing how effective they considered the STEP platform to be for viewing the ideas of other young people

The platform also scored well on being able to see the ideas of other young people with no-one disagreeing and 84% agreeing that the platform was effective in this respect.

Fig 2.6 Combined Survey data showing young people's opinion on how effective the STEP platform is for increasing Trust between Young People and Policy Makers/Public Officers

A less positive response was given for how effective the platform was for increasing trust of local policy makers with the majority of people remaining neutral on this (58%), 10% disagreed and 33% agreed. More in depth questioning of YECs suggests that trust will only be gained after positive actions are seen after the Dialogues.

Fig 2.7 Chart showing gender balance of the YECs participating in the surveys

The gender of the survey participants is well balanced with 53% male : 47% female

Fig 2.8 Chart showing employment status of the YECs participating in the surveys

The employment status of the survey participants is mixture of students (53% full-time, 5% part-time) and full-time employed people (37%), 5% caring duties (young child).

2.5.2 Policy Maker Responses:

Email requests were made to the Local Pilot partners involved in the STEP project to complete the Public Officer Survey for the relevant Dialogue that they had been involved with and to share the survey (created in Google Forms) with their colleagues (not directly involved in the project) who had also been using the platform. Surveys had been translated into local languages.

2.5.2.1 Valdemoro Policy Makers Call for Ideas Survey

Four public authority officials completed this survey in Valdemoro after being involved in a 'Call for Ideas' Dialogue: Two of these were from the local Education Department, one was local government administration and one worked in technological innovation / technical management. 3 of the 4 were aged 35-44 and one aged 45-54. 3 of the 4 were male and one female.

Of the 4 policy makers, two remained neutral on the question (4) asking if they agreed that the platform was **easy to use**, one person agreed and one strongly agreed. (**Slightly Positive**).

The response to the question (5) asking if the platform would be likely to **increase youth participation** was very mixed, with one person disagreeing, one neutral, one agreeing & one strongly agreeing. (**Neutral**).

When asked about the platform being **able to reach all sectors** of the target audience (including the hard to reach) then again the response was mixed, one person strongly disagreed, one agreed and two were neutral. (**Neutral**). Relating to this question was Q7, asking if they thought that the people participating in the STEP call/dialogues were representative of the young population as a whole 3 people (75%) were neutral and one person strongly disagreed. (**Negative**).

For question 8, all participants **agreed** that the STEP platform would allow policy makers to:

- Quickly obtain ideas from young people on environmental issues
- Gain a better understanding of the views of young people
- Engage young people with environmental policy making (**ALL Positive**)

Respondents were less enthusiastic about the **impact** of the call for ideas dialogue however; when asked if the results of the call for ideas made through STEP had a **real impact on the decisions and policies** of the Municipality then 2 people were neutral, one disagreed and one strongly disagreed with the statement. (**Negative**).

Q10 asked if they would recommend the STEP platform to others in a similar position, one person disagreed 2 agreed and one strongly agreed (**Positive**).

Q11 asked if they would **use the platform again** to obtain ideas from Young people; 1 person strongly disagreed, 2 agreed and 1 strongly agreed (**Mostly Positive**).

Q 12 responses to open ended question on what would have been useful to include:

- Better integration with social networks
- More previous work with groups of young people sensitized before launching the platform

There was no response to Q13 (free-text question), which asked if there was anything that would prevent them from using the platform again. Question 14 asked if the platform was likely to increase **trust** between Young people and policy makers; responses were – 1 disagree, 1 neutral and 2 agree (**slightly Positive**).

Other Comments: “The platform should be **more intuitive** to facilitate its use”.

2.5.2.2 Crete Call for Ideas Survey

(3 responses) All respondees stated their job was Local Government Management, 2 were female and one male.

Of the 3 respondees, one disagreed with the question asking if the platform was **easy to use**, the other two strongly agreed. (**Mostly Positive**).

The response to the question (5) asking if the platform would be likely to **increase youth participation** was mostly positive with one neutral response & two strongly agreeing. (**Positive**).

When asked about the platform being **able to reach all sectors** of the target audience (including the hard to reach) all strongly agreed. (**Very Positive**). Relating to this question was Q7, asking if they thought that the people participating in the STEP call/dialogues were **representative** of the young population as a whole; one person was neutral and one agreed and one person strongly agreed. (**Positive**).

For question 8, all participants **agreed** that the STEP platform would allow policy makers to:

- Quickly obtain ideas from young people on environmental issues
One agreed and 2 strongly agreed – (**Very Positive**)
- Gain a better understanding of the views of young people
One disagreed, 2 strongly agreed (**Mostly Positive**)
- Engage young people with environmental policy making
Two people neutral one strongly agreed (**slightly Positive**)

When asked if the results of the call for ideas made through STEP had a **real impact on the decisions and policies** adopted by the region then one person was neutral, one agreed and one strongly agreed (**Positive**)

Q10 asked if they would recommend the STEP platform to others in a similar position, 2 people agreed and one strongly agreed (**Positive**).

Q11 asked if they would **use the platform again** to obtain ideas from Young people; 1 person agreed and 2 strongly agreed (**Very Positive**).

No comments on any features that were not available (Q12)

Q 13 Comments on anything that would hinder use of the platform: 'The mobile android application is unmanageable' the other response was nothing hindering use.

Question 14 asked if the platform was likely to increase **trust** between Young people and policy makers; all 3 strongly agreed (**Very Positive**).

2.5.2.3 Crete Consultation Process Survey

(2 responses) Both respondees stated their job was Local Government Management, and both were female.

A mixed response was given for Q4, the statement 'Using the STEP platform for a consultation process was simple' with one person strongly disagreeing and one strongly agreeing. (**Neutral**)

The response to the question (5) asking if the platform would be likely to **increase youth participation** was mostly positive with one neutral and one strongly agreeing. (**mostly positive**).

When asked about the platform being **able to reach all sectors** of the target audience (including the hard to reach) then the response was very positive, with both people strongly agreeing (**Very Positive**). Relating to this question was Q7, asking if they thought that the people participating in the STEP call/dialogues were representative of the young population as a whole , one person was neutral and one person strongly agreed. (**Mostly Positive**).

For question 8, that the STEP platform would allow policy makers to:

- Quickly obtain ideas from young people on environmental issues
One person strongly disagreed, the other strongly agreed
- Gain a better understanding of the views of young people
One person strongly disagreed, the other strongly agreed
- Engage young people with environmental policy making
One person strongly disagreed, the was neutral

Q10 asked if they believed that the results of the consultation process conducted via STEP had had a real impact on the decisions and policies of the region; one person was neutral and one agreed.

When asked if they would recommend STEP to people in a similar position to themselves, then both people strongly agreed.

There was no response to the question on missing features.

For the question on increasing trust, one person disagreed and one strongly agreed that the STEP platform was likely to increase trust between local government and young people.

Comments received:

The app is inconvenient. The user has difficulty understanding the functions. They appear mixed Greek and English. Although it is called Step, it needs extensive search to find the page in google.

2.5.2.4 Hatay Call for Ideas Survey

A total of 8 people (Public officers) responded to the Call for Ideas Survey, 4 males & 4 females, fig 2.9 below shows the distribution of job types of the participants.

Fig 2.9 Hatay Public Officer Job titles

Fig 2.10 Chart showing Hatay Public Officer opinion on the usability of the STEP platform

Fig 2.11 Chart showing Hatay Public Officer opinion on the efficacy of the STEP platform

Fig 2.12 Chart showing the Public Officer opinion of the efficacy of the STEP platform to reach young people

Fig 2.13 Chart showing the Public Officer opinion of the efficacy of the STEP platform to engage young people

Fig 2.14 Chart showing if Public Officers would use the STEP platform again

Fig 2.15 Chart showing the Public Officer opinion of the efficacy of the STEP platform to increase the participation of YP

Hatay Public Officers rated the STEP platform very highly, all agreeing or strongly agreeing that they would use it again, that it would be likely to increase the participation of young people. They also all agreed or strongly agreed that the platform was straightforward to use and that STEP is useful in engaging YP in policy making and would be likely to increase the participation of young people.

Comments: Missing features - 'Delete record feature' 'Full awareness of the environment to young people'

The second comment refers to having more educational material available to inform the young STEP users about the issues under discussion / consultation. Perhaps links to reputable websites with more information. A feature that was also mentioned in the interviews with Hatay policy makers.

Hatay Public Officers rated the STEP platform the most highly of all the Pilot Regions, in the survey above no-one really had any negative ratings, although they said that more material to inform young people on environmental issues could be available. The Hatay public officers interviewed did offer a little more criticism when interviewed, but this mostly related to the difficulty of recruiting young people to take part in the Pilot Dialogues.

2.6 Interviews

Structured Interviews (see Appendix A for Interview questions) were carried out to evaluate the platform in greater depth with small samples of both young people and policy makers/public officers from the various Pilot Cities. From the interviews the general perception was that the platform was attractive and the young people who were interviewed said that they had enjoyed using it. However, they also said that it was less intuitive than it could be and that the process of registering and getting onto the platform seemed a bit complicated (that they were used to quick and easy access using existing social media log-ins). Finding for the app was also mentioned as being quite difficult. Young people enjoyed seeing the posts made by other young people and felt that the platform would be useful to bring together people to connect and share ideas. They felt it could promote a 'sense of responsibility' for taking care of the environment.

For the public officers who were interviewed, they voiced concerns over the length of time it was taking to raise awareness of the platform to the target group. They raised concerns over usability and technical issues of the platform and some municipalities mentioned that as the platform was not an integrated component of their current software then staff would be less likely to engage with it (Hatay). Public Officers felt that setting up a new dialogue for the first time could be challenging, help videos are available, but usually people want to just complete the task without accessing any help. It was mentioned that there was a lot of different functionality within the platform, but mostly public officers were using a small subset of this (Ideas/Petitions/Consultations) and not really making full use of the rest.

Table 2.2 showing number of people participating in the Evaluation Interviews

Interviews	Young People	Public Officers	Total
Mollet	1	1 (1 PO & 1 Politician)	3
Valdemoro	1	1	2
Crete	-	1	1
Hatay	2	2	4
Locride	-	2	2

The main issues from these interviews have been identified below:

2.6.1. Issues Identified by YECs:

- Uncertainty over the function of the Platform – the name STEP does not denote anything about eParticipation.
- Difficulty in searching for the platform online / app store (Would prefer to have a local search term. Including the name Mollet - MDV)
- The platform is often quite slow to run
- Not as intuitive as it could be.
- Users didn't know that you could comment on the posts already made (Comments under posts not visible enough)
- Users could not find the Issue reporting mechanism (now resolved)
- Some users were not sure about sharing STEP posts to Social Media ('if there is one, I did not find it – to me it's not clear')

- Link to platform is too long (for Mollet). This long name for the link (Mollet) suggests ‘this is not for me’. Name too hard to remember. (MDV)
- For some pilots, where a specific longer link is being used, this is not memorable and is a potential **barrier to uptake**.

Figure 2.16 Banner showing long link to Mollet STEP platform

2.6.2 Positive Platform Features Identified by YECs:

- Interesting to meet other YP who can work together.
- Best thing is to bring together the different citizens from different parts of society to connect and share ideas.
- It is fun to use.
- I think the phone app was pretty straightforward to use, it was clear what I needed to do.
- Enjoyed seeing everyone else’s ideas.
- Works well for the Dialogues and it’s easy to make a post.
- Liked the gamification aspects (but would also like more).
- The platform is a positive voice helping to connect people and to give a sense of community or union between citizens locally and from different countries.
- It’s important to gather people together to join forces for the things we want to change and this platform helps.
- It’s great that it feels pretty familiar and it doesn’t require a great deal of effort to participate.
- Can export ideas from other places.
- We are in a time where we are more interconnected. Good to have the possibility to communicate with others speaking a different language
- Like the familiar feel (similar to social media platforms).
- Help features are useful
- Platform is helping to build a ‘Sense of Responsibility’ for the environment that we all share

2.6.3 Policy Maker / Municipality Issues Identified:

Technical / Usability Issues

- YP have no idea what the platform does at first glance. We would prefer to have 'Participate' or 'Decide' in the title
- There was a technical issue preventing inviting young people to a new Dialogue (it was being done via What's App / Facebook and other social media platforms). Issue now resolved.
- Not always clear where the posts came from (Social Media Monitoring Tool - SMMT) PO's reported that young people not sure about the 'crowley green' web crawler term.
- The fact that the Dialogues are running in 'Private' mode (Mollet).
- Map view of the Dialogues may hide the posts made.
- In the app people cannot see the video links or comments (hidden lower down and need to scroll). Would prefer the video to be at the top of the post and not the bottom.
- Likes/comments should also be more visible – ideally at the top.
- Language / translation issues hindered usability.
- Should be providing the YP with more opportunity to inform them on environmental issues. For example, if the Dialogues is about creating more green space then have a link showing how this has been achieved in other cities.
- Would be helpful to have a channel / announcement area showing YP how to get involved in voluntary work in their local area.
- Occasional technical errors in the Platform (e.g. slow upload time, Social Media Monitoring Tool not available at times).
- The difficulties in downloading the app are a problem for YP (from a Policy Maker)
- Heavy requirements of the App, YP do not always have sufficient space on their phones. Web version preferred. (from a Policy Maker)
- The usability issues are a barrier to use, usability needs to be improved . Not as intuitive as it could be.
- Web platform feels 'too big', Users could get lost.
- The need to support young people to download the STEP app and instruct them how to participate in a dialogue (taking a lot of time).
- Pilots are needing to incentivise YP to use the platform (prize draws for bikes / tablets / vouchers etc).

Cultural Issues:

- Having the STEP platform does not change people overnight. Culture of the Municipality staff will take a long time to change. Slow evolution rather than transformation.
- Municipality staff are not used to this type of Open Consultation.
- Mismatch between length of time YP expect to see a result and the time taken for the municipality to act on the Dialogues.
- Municipality / Town Hall - giving a quick response after a dialogue is important.
- Success of the Dialogue is dependent on the amount of effort that municipality staff put in to contributing to the Dialogue discussions (encouragement).
- Pilots needing active PR campaigns to promote the platform (costly & time consuming).

- YP Need to feel empowered and to know ‘What Happens Now’.
- Public Sector moves Very Slowly.
- For YP Seeing the results and actions will be the key to the success of the platform.
- Need extra support for Policy Makers to use the advanced admin features (not all are technically inclined). Extra training session has now been organised for the beginning of July.

2.6.4 Positive Municipality Features Identified

- Outputs other than those produced from the Dialogues themselves – eg. The creation of a group of volunteers to advise and be involved in the management of the Gallecs Park (Mollet). This group was created from active participants of a Dialogue discussing the park, but was not an expected outcome or goal at the start.
- Positive outcomes from the Platform will improve the receptiveness of municipality staff to future Dialogues.
- It’s a simpler way to run Participatory Budget Planning.
- The participatory budget planning (via voting) worked really well and attracted a lot of interest (Mollet).
- Good to see the high number of young people now engaging with the dialogues (Hatay).
- Great to have this line of communication with the young people in the local area

2.7 Usability Testing of the Platform

The difficulties faced in the development of software, screen media and large-scale public engagement projects of how to get feedback from all user groups, stakeholders and developers quickly, unobtrusively and effectively has been discussed in the previous deliverable (D5.1). The STEP Platform with its main functionalities was available and ready as planned during February 2017. However there were minor bugs such as broken links to download mobile apps, invitation email issues, translation quality issues that had to be solved by the pilots during the launch. This along with the lack of tutorials for Public Officer administrators to manage their dialogues meant that there was a short delay before the pilots were able to launch the dialogues on the. These issues have now been resolved during the launch period and pilots started their official dialogues in March 2017. Tutorials are now available for the various features of the platform and can be found in the advanced admin section of the platform and this should resolve many difficulties that Public Officers faced initially due to their lack of familiarity with the platform.

As part of the effort to improve the usability of the platform, more user testing is planned to ensure any issues are picked up and corrected in a timely manner. Unfortunately due to the unforeseen delays in the development process, the ABCD reporting tool that we planned to utilise was late in being implemented. The platform functionality itself (ie posting to a Dialogue), was used in place of this by the various project partners and this has in fact captured many issues. However, this method was not really an option for capturing in situ User Feedback from the early interactions of Young People with the Pilot Dialogues. This issue has now been addressed with the ABCD issue reporting form now being an integrated component of the STEP platform to enable ease of use, we will capture feedback from more end-users during the next phase of the project. We believe that participants could be encouraged to send reports by having this contribute to the gamification aspects of the platform (ie the participant will receive points for reporting), encouraging them to make reports.

Some usability testing was done by STEP project staff to try and find issues within the platform. Issues were sent as a report via email to the developers initially, and later added as entries as and when an issue was found after the Issue Reporting Dialogue was set up. Usability issues were also collected by attending the training sessions between developers and Pilot partners in charge of implementing the Dialogues and noting down the issues that were being discussed.

The images and text below show a sample of issues identified during the early usability testing process.

- I am still getting the Greek default language when I enter the platform
- When I am in account/myfeed then the large picture of the attractive girls takes you away from the platform and links to <http://www.kairosfuture.com/academy/courses/> Kairos courses – is this intentional?

Fig 2.17 Link to participate in surveys that took users away from the main STEP platform to a Kairos Futures web page

Text suggests that the user will stay within the STEP platform but move to another discussion – this doesn't happen though. It's too easy to accidentally leave the platform.

- For the Social Media Monitoring – I still cannot drag & drop my existing tags onto the 'Place your tags' section

Fig 2.18 Issue Reporting Problem – Suggested Fix on the right showing Feedback option for MyDay platform with good visibility.

Fig 2.19 Mix of English / Greek on the platform despite English option being chosen

Fig 2.20 Screenshot showing Issue Reporting via STEP Dialogue

STEP platform Issue Reporting		
Functionality	Issue Reported	Action
Set Up / Profiles	Difficulty deleting profiles	Ensure profiles can be deleted – now implemented for next release
Social Media Monitoring Tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty Accessing SMMT • Keyword Entry Issues • Start Search button issue • Speed issues 	Improve the functionality of the SMMT to address the issues identified (still to improve this)
Dialogues Multimedia option	YP want to post multimedia in response to other posts – currently only text reply	Allow multimedia uploads in response to posts (not just new posts)
Reaching Young People	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty inviting YP to dialogue No mechanism for letting YP know when a new dialogue is posted	Push notification is now implemented for inviting YP and for informing them of new dialogues
Sharing Social Media	Irrelevant images associated with post	Correct – provide clearer images
Europe-Wide Timeline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usability issue with Post-it-Notes Issue with ‘Engage in other Surveys’ link	Amended appropriately
Machine Translation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Android app mixing languages • Localisation issues (eg word order) • Native accent issues (Catalan) • Issue Turkish characters 	Bugs fixed Pilots were able to fix translation issues by manually translating some text.
Issue Reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mechanism for issue reporting not visible enough Only available to Policy makers/project partners – not young people	Make more visible : Place at top of Screen & ensure high contrast

Figure 2.21 Table showing Issues reported via STEP platform by Pilots / STEP project staff

For the next phase of evaluation the feedback mechanism is now more visible to encourage its use). Giving feedback to participants on how the issue reports will improve the system is also recommended and we believe it will encourage the ‘Sense of Community’ that is important in user engagement with the platform, encouraging use and young people’s willingness to share information via the platform and ultimately to the improvement of the platform itself. Feedback should also be encouraged by using the points system in the gamification mechanism.

2.7.1 Cognitive walk-throughs / User testing

Now that the Pilots have launched dialogues, more detailed user testing in the form of Cognitive walk-throughs or ‘think-aloud’ protocols will be conducted. Think-aloud protocols involving participants thinking aloud as they are performing a set of specified tasks and was introduced into the usability field by Clayton Lewis (1982). Participants are asked to say whatever comes into their mind as they complete the task, giving observers an insight into the participant's cognitive processes. This has now been carried out with some public officers in charge of setting up the STEP dialogues.

2.7.2 Example of Pilot Dialogue (Hatay Park Dialogue)

The posts from the Park Dialogue in Hatay were downloaded as a document (this was new functionality requested after the Cultural Probe activity). The text was then cleaned (removing the dates and names of the people posting) then the text was translated to English. Remaining clean text was analysed in Voyant (<https://voyant-tools.org/>) to highlight the most commonly used words and the context of their use.

Fig 2.22 Screenshot showing some of the early Hatay Dialogues

	Term	Count			
			11	neighborhood	8
1	park	25	12	trees	8
2	children	20	13	free	7
3	areas	15	14	young	7
4	parks	15	15	activities	6
5	people	14	16	certain	6
6	area	11	17	nice	6
7	hatay	11	18	places	6
8	small	9	19	read	6
9	book	8	20	special	6
10	make	8			

Fig 2.25 Most used words in the Hatay Park Dialogue

3.0 Early Insights from the Intermediate Evaluation Process

These preliminary findings can help the STEP project to make the most from the final months of the Pilot Trials.

It is evident that there is a large variation in Youth Engagement across the Pilot regions, as well as differences in response to the various Dialogues. Early indications are that the Dialogues resulting in Young People posting images (eg Hatay dialogue) have worked well and attracted large response rates. Another example of a very successful Dialogue has been the questionnaire dialogue where citizens have voting for which local area to be renovated with an award of 100,000 Euros to carry out the work (in Mollet del Valles).

It is evident from the survey and interview responses that the young people are interested in what other young people have to say on the platform, and the opportunity to have their voice heard by the relevant local government / public officer is valuable. However, the number of people interacting with the platform for some of the pilots is lower than anticipated and the need for greater awareness of the platform is apparent. There has been a very good response to some questionnaires posted by the Pilot cities, but as the results are less immediately visible (to other young citizens) perhaps these Dialogues should follow the image posting type that seem to be so successful in fostering engagement, as the images are attractive and are what young people expect to see. In addition greater use could be made of advertising on the popular social media sites.

Initially we were concerned as there appeared to be a lower number of participants than expected after many Pilots had spent considerable time attracting young people to join the platform. This was a reflection on how the platform had been recording 'participants' on the system. It has become apparent that users may be actively signed in, reading posts, liking /commenting on posts and even completing surveys proposed by the Pilots without being recorded as a 'participant'. The platform settings had been for YP only to be added as a participant if they made a specific post. As many pilots were asking them to fill in surveys they

were not being displayed as active participants. It had caused concern to Pilot partners though who felt that people were being ‘lost’ in the system. The participants contributing to questionnaires and other features other than ‘posts’ can now be counted through the advanced admin features of the platform where the number of people can be seen, how many dialogues they have joined, how many posts they have made and if they have posted to a ‘timeline’ feature. The number of people interacting is now clearer to the Pilot’s who can now assess the success of each Dialogue based on the interaction.

3.1.0 Moving Forward to the next Evaluation Phase

Given some of the early difficulties encountered for this first phase of evaluation, plans are now in place not only to address the issues highlighted in this report, but to ensure a greater reach for the evaluation process. As all the Pilots are now actively running dialogues and attracting more users, we feel confident that a much greater number of users will contribute to the ongoing evaluation process. We have calculated the numbers of people we need to complete the surveys to obtain any statistically significant results in the next period of evaluation (shown in the table below).

		Ideal Sample Size	Minimum Sample Size
	Young People Total Involved	95% Confidence Level & 5% Margin Error	95% Confidence Level & 10% Margin Error
Italy	1500	306	91
Spain	1200	292	89
Greece	3000	341	94
Turkey	3500	347	94

Increased efforts will also be paid to carrying out more Usability Testing, plans to run usability tests with Policy Makers/Public Officers are in place for early July and testing with YECs will also be undertaken. Help videos have been created to support Public officers (found at <http://www.akoscep.com/step-admin/10.html>) but a more visible link to this support would be preferable as it’s currently quite difficult to find them.

In addition, the separate components of the STEP platform (ie Social Media Mining Tool, Machine Translation functionality, Chat functionality etc.) will be evaluated. A longer survey considering these will give more in-depth information on both the usability and technical issues that were encountered as well as evaluating how useful the stakeholders found them to be.

3.1.1 Main Issues to be Addressed

As this is a new platform there have of course, been early setbacks and issues to be dealt with. We feel that so far young people using the platform have made a lot of positive comments about the platform and how useful it will be, however we will of course focus on areas for improvement. After considering the issues

identified by young people and Policy Makers, the issues below should be considered a priority to ensure a more successful Platform and to achieve greater eParticipation.

- ❖ The number of users is a little low for some Pilots, others are reaching targets. Support to be given to pilots with lower numbers.
- ❖ The fact that the purpose of the platform is confusing to some young people.
- ❖ Usability could be further improved. More user testing is needed and the newly released issue reporting tool will support this.
- ❖ Comments made on the Posts should be more visible (even 1 line of text to show that they are there). This should encourage greater interaction between Young People.
- ❖ 'Map view' of the Dialogues hides the posts made making interaction less likely.
- ❖ What represents a user? For example, people are signing up and completing dialogue surveys. Young people are participating, but not being counted as a participant. Currently only recorded as a user if making a post. Agreed to change this to reflect the different kinds of participation.
- ❖ Pilots reported a requirement for extra training to use the many admin features of the STEP platform. (Now arranged for 1st week in July).
- ❖ Need to have Push notifications for informing YP of when New Dialogues are released (Pilots had resorted to using email & WhatsApp) . Issue now fixed.
- ❖ Greater use of gamification aspects to encourage participation and the users to return to the platform a second time. (Focus on Gamification features mid-June – see section 3.1.2 for recommendations).
- ❖ Platform should offer more opportunity for a 'bottom up' approach to participation. The requested chat feature is now implemented.
- ❖ Speed of Response from Public Officers/Municipality is Critical.
- ❖ Time required for successful dialogues, at least in the early stages is high, requiring encouragement from the dialogue owner(s) – Pilots need to allow for this.

3.1.1.1 Other Possible Actions:

- ❖ Have the other Pilot cities replicate Hatay's dialogue about posting areas of beauty in the local regions for Youth Engagement & Awareness raising. Although this is not a decision making process, it is effective in building up interest amongst young people, and the best of the images could be used as backgrounds for the STEP platform. The image posting is a very good activity for engagement which more closely matches the expectations of YP for an interactive platform. This is now being replicated in Crete
- ❖ Encourage more interaction of young people to discuss the ideas shared (eg. highlight the more active posts and latest activities on the platform, for example make use of the 'Events' functionality which allows this to be displayed).
- ❖ Making use of short video recordings to encourage use – ideally of a young person (local to the Pilot region) inviting other YP to join the Dialogues. This has been very successful in Mollet.
- ❖ Make use of the 'Embeddable Snippets' functionality to highlight the STEP platform on more Social Media Platforms and on Municipality websites (training on this to be provided in July).

3.1.2 Recommendations for Gamification Aspects of STEP

1. Ensure transparency of the points system. Make it clearer how users are allocated points (even just by having a table explaining point allocation in the Help section)
2. Make the leaderboard visible if it is currently hidden on the dialogues (option is available to Pilots via advanced admin to either show/hide this).
3. Leaderboard: Ideally reduce (or hide) the points given to the Public Officers; by the nature of their active involvement with the dialogues they almost always appear at the top of the leaderboard. It would be better to restrict this to the young people themselves.
4. Explain the 'Dialogue Score' & 'Profile Score'
5. Utilise the points mechanism /gamification to allow the most active users of the Platform (YECs) greater admin rights, for example – once they reach a certain level they will be able to create their own dialogue on the platform. This supports the recommendation for Youth empowerment and Leadership opportunities mentioned earlier.

3.1.2.1 Possible Future Directions (outwith the current scope of the STEP platform)

6. Introduce a recommendation system – eg people who posted on/ liked 'x' also posted on/ liked 'y' – this would prompt further interaction within the platform – perhaps suggesting actions in other dialogues that YECs may be interested in. Creating this type of 'trigger' for further action could increase participation and lead to increased interest of young people. This issue was discussed with the developers who said that currently it is too difficult to implement. However there is an option in advanced admin to allow 'other active dialogues currently available' to be shown on the user's page. This information will be shared with Pilot partners to encourage greater interaction of YP with the existing dialogues once a user enters the STEP platform.

3.2 STEP platform updates

This section describes the STEP Platform updates during the reporting period. STEP Platform provides two different feature sets for Public Administrations and Citizens.

Public Administrations (PA) are able to provide their own dialogues within their own STEP sites. Each public administration is able to create their own web site/space under STEP Platform. Pilot cities localized their own STEP portals in their own languages including Turkish, Greek, Spanish, Catalan and Italian. All information sections on the STEP portal are translated into supported platform languages and available in pilot regions with their own languages. Pilots sites are reachable as follows:

- Region of Crete: <https://gr.step.green/crete>
- Hatay Metropolitan Municipality: <https://tr.step.green/hatay>

- Assoc. of the Communities of Locride: <https://it.step.green/locride>
- Mollet des Valles Municipality: <https://cat.step.green/mollet>
- Valdemoro Municipality: <https://es.step.green/Valdemoro>
- Thessaloniki Pilot: <https://tr.step.green/thessaloniki>

PA users are able to manage their existing dialogues using archiving, removal, data management and public/private dialogues management sections. PAs are allowed to create three types of dialogues in STEP: e-Petition, Consultation, Idea Generation and invitation and easy inline editing features of dialogues made the platform user friendly for PA users.

Other features for PAs usage are as follows:

- Map Your Ideas, Round Table, Chat (Messaging), Questionnaire, Timeline
- My Page & Social Media Mining & Monitoring Tool
- Machine Translation & Text to Speech
- Post Management (like, comment, score, edit/copy/move post), Email/Push Notification, Signatures, Reporting
- Embeddable Snippets (Embedding into Municipality Web Sites)
- Advanced Admin Features

Citizens reach the platform through either the step.green landing page or directly using the pilot web sites. The STEP platform provides easy registration and login features via email or via their existing social media accounts. Citizens are allowed to join and reach public and private dialogues of pilot PAs and post their ideas, petitions to dialogues. Citizens are allowed to share their petitions by e-mail or social media platforms to gain support (signatures). They are able to track what's trending in Social Media using Social Media Monitoring and Mining tool embedded into their own STEP pages. They can also track their scores using user profile and leader board features and able to use general STEP features and dialogues like: General usage for all European Youngsters, For a Greener Europe, Put your idea on a map, Timeline features.

Web and social media mining component presents emerging topics from social media and the web relevant to users' interests is available at Admin menu at step.green for PAs and available at My Page as embedded for all citizens interested topics. For PAs, a visualization component is provided which presents external content has been developed. It includes map and timeline based visualisations to help the analysts to identify the spatial distribution of use contributed content, the origin of certain trends and their evolution over time. Main updates in Web and social media mining part are as follows:

- User management integrated in the tool: Each user (admin or young) creates its own collections
- De-duplication of content added: The user has the ability to see only original content by using the appropriate filter in the UI
- Redesign of start/stop/edit of collection: The user can start / stop a collection on demand, Can edit a collection to include / exclude tags & users, Pagination of collections
- Support of logical operations as input: The user can use logical expressions as input instead of simple tags E.g. ('air pollution' OR 'climate change') AND ('donald trump')
- Performance issues: HTTP caching added to decrease response time of complex queries, MongoDB storage updated to use new db engine
- Improved topic detection: Use information of text's language
- Supported pilots' languages: en, es, el, tr, it

Machine Translation and Text to Speech Component provides dynamic content accessibility and readability in pilots own languages. STEP Text to Speech (TTS) technology is now ready with all features enabling text to be read to the user for English, Spanish, Italian, Greek, Turkish and Catalan. STEP Machine Translation (MT) technology is enabling to translate step.green dynamic/user provided content in pilot countries languages. (English, Spanish, Italian, Greek, Turkish and Catalan)

STEP Mobile

Both TTS and MT Technologies are also adapted into Android platform and now available for mobile users. Speed and quality of MT is improved esp. in Turkish and Catalan languages.

The STEP Platform also provides enhanced mobile interfaces via native iOS and Android applications. These applications are available on the App Store and Google Play Store markets. They can also be reached easily via “step.green” keywords. Applications provide multi-lingual interfaces, social media integration and interaction with dialogues through their own mobile devices.

Fig 3.0 STEP Mobile Application

3.3 Addressing the Specific Challenges to eParticipation

According to the recent European Parliament Report (Potential and Challenges of eParticipation in the European Union, 2016) one of the biggest challenges for e-participation is European **citizens' disinterest** in EU politics, including the **lack of trust** in the EU (and the belief that the EU cannot solve their problems). This also represents a more general challenge since **eParticipation tools tend to have a very low participation rate at national levels**. The other significant challenge is that these e-participation **tools are simply unknown to citizens**. The first issue is quite difficult to address and will take time and probably many positive engagement experiences to change; the second can be addressed much more easily by Awareness Raising and informing Young People in a timely and appropriate way about how to engage with the STEP platform to ensure their voice is heard.

The report states that eParticipation tools can represent an alternative form of engagement for citizens who are tired of ‘traditional politics’ and help promote more grassroots support for EU policy. The democratic deficit should be grasped as an opportunity for the EU to show that it cares about its citizens by giving them the possibility to participate in the decision-making process in a more collaborative manner’. It seems that Young People are the group most likely to be ‘tired of traditional politics’ so the use of STEP to encourage engagement is well directed.

To support the Pilot partners in meeting these challenges, and in engaging young people in the eParticipation processes, recommendations were made earlier in the project. Certain crucial aspects are common to all e-participation processes, and these were highlighted in a previous STEP deliverable (D4.1).

These are:

🔴 Alignment with young people’s realities

eParticipation processes need to be aligned with young people’s lives. This relates to matters such as content, information and time management, but also to design and technical implementation. The processes should be designed to interest, stimulate and motivate young people to ensure their continuing involvement.

🔴 Resources

eParticipation processes require sufficient resources such as expertise, time, funding and technology, as well as staff to provide guidance and advisory services.

🔴 Effectiveness & direct influence

eParticipation processes need to have an outcome. A structural link to decision-making processes is essential.

🔴 Transparency

The overall process needs to be transparent for everyone. This requirement extends to all information related to the process as well as to the software and tools used.

🔴 End-to-end involvement of young people

Young people need to be involved in all stages of the process. This includes a feedback option in all phases of the process.

3.4 *How the Pilot’s are aligning with Youth Engagement Recommendations*

- 🔴 **FOCUS ON ISSUES OF INTEREST:** Focus the bootstrap-piloting of the platform on the discussion of policies/issues that are of direct interest to YP:
 - The earlier STEP research carried out for D2.4 contributed to an understanding of the type of issues that Young People may be interested in discussing on the STEP platform. Each of the Pilot’s was also able to make use of the Social Media Monitoring Tool to gain up-to-date knowledge of the issues that people are discussing on Social Media in their region. Some Pilots also consulted local schools and Youth Groups to find out what issues were of concern to young people in their region.

🔴 **START SMALL AND BUILD UP:**

- The first e-Participation processes trialled by the Pilots were smaller scale and were of a simple nature with clearly defined guidelines. For example, in Mollet young people were asked what type of plants to grow in the community allotments; in Locride the purpose of initial Dialogues was to ask about better waste recycling; in Valdemoro the issue was a new cycling route; in Crete there was an early Dialogue about saving energy and in Hatay young people were asked to post positive images of the local environment.

🔴 **PROMOTE TRUST:**

- As the timescale for the Pilot eParticipation processes is quite short it is unlikely that a significant increase in trust will be achieved. The various short Dialogues promoted by the Pilots may however, help to begin to build trust, especially if Young People feel they had an influence on the outcome of the process and that they had their voice heard. Ensuring the process is as open and transparent as possible should also promote trust building. We are asking about trust on the evaluation surveys and also in the interviews, preliminary results suggest that, at this stage, it is too early to see any increase in trust levels and that this will only happen once young people see actions resulting from the Dialogues and that their contributions have led to actions.
- From the interviews undertaken so far, the opinion of Public Officers / Politician is that the Platform will help to build trust between young people and the Municipality/ Local Region. The threat identified here is the mismatch between the time taken for the municipalities to act and the time that Young People expect a response to their contributions made on the platform. This will need to be managed well, with early feedback given to the young people involved, informing them of actions that will occur in time.
- With each cycle of Dialogues made by the municipality that achieve good engagement from Young People, then trust should slowly develop. It will not happen immediately, but should develop over time as long as both the platform and municipalities perform well.

🔴 **PROMOTE EMPOWERMENT & LEADERSHIP:** STEP should offer opportunities for empowerment and leadership: young people should feel that their action is meaningful and helps make a difference. Give feedback; inform young people how their actions have made a difference, state how any information was used and highlight any actions following a consultation.

- In Mollet, one of the positive outcomes of an early Dialogue was the forming of a local advisory group of young people for the Gallecs / Can Borrell facility. The platform helped to identify young people taking a leadership role and who would be willing to contribute to this local action.
- Pilots would like to enable the activist participants of STEP (ie. those participating on the platform a lot) the opportunity to have extra functionality on the platform, for example be able to set up calls for actions (perhaps looking for volunteers for an environmental activity), create group chats and to launch their own Dialogues. This would support a more 'bottom-up approach' that would be more empowering and would encourage active participants to take on a leadership role. This will be investigated and developed further for the next iteration of the software.

- **NURTURE EXISTING PARTNERSHIPS:** Utilise existing Youth / Environmental Organisations, partnerships; these should be nurtured where possible. In the first place integrate where possible with Youth Environment Europe (YEE) who have over 40,000 members and are partners in the project, but also if possible local NGO's in the pilot municipalities.
 - All Pilots have good contacts with existing volunteering /environmental groups, for example Civitas Solis (Calabria), Genç TEMA (Hatay), and also with local schools (MDV & Valdemoro) and are making use of these partnerships to increase awareness of the STEP platform.

- **UTILISE APPROPRIATE MECHANISMS:**
 - Mechanisms to increase youth engagement will be incorporated as part of the platform. STEP will utilise gamification techniques such as the leaderboard and point system and we will evaluate if young people felt that this actually increased engagement with the platform.
 - Early indications are that the Young People like the Leaderboard and that it encourages engagement. Gamification aspects will be looked at in more detail for the next report (D5.3). Some gamification ideas were put forward in the co-design work and we are examining these ideas and collaborating with an expert in the area of gamification for eParticipation to promote greater use of this aspect of the platform for youth engagement.
 - The mechanism to create the leaderboard will be utilized to support the empowerment and leadership roles discussed above. It should be made more transparent how the process works, different levels will be reached when points are obtained through participatory activities on the platform. At the minute it is not clear to young people how points are obtained, this should be rectified (increasing transparency).

- **KEEP BARRIERS TO PARTICIPATION LOW:** Make it quick and easy for young people to access the STEP platform from other social media sites, log-in should be optional to view platform content. Allowing them a choice of participation methods will increase engagement.
 - Pilots have released Dialogues aiming to engage Young People without asking too much from them at this early stage. For example, in Mollet the Dialogue about the allotments at Can Borrell asked young people to share what their favourite fruits / vegetables were to see what could be planted. Choice of filling in the short survey and/or uploading an image and making a post. Many short surveys have been deployed where users could vote without having to first sign up or log-in to the platform, making it quick and easy for them to participate.

- **DEVELOP A SENSE OF COMMUNITY:** There are no definitive answers as to how to go about this, but questions regarding youth identification and belonging should try and be addressed as a starting point. The ability to create common goals and purpose is important.

- This **'sense of community'** has been an important aspect of the early Dialogues put forward by the Pilots. It can be seen from the posts that the young people are clearly proud of their local environments. For example, one of the Hatay Dialogues asks people to 'uncover the beautiful aspects of the Hatay local environment', and promised to display the best images on the Landing page of the STEP platform. This dialogue received a very good response. This dialogue not only promotes a **'sense of community'** but also promotes **'hope for the future'** which was another important aspect discussed by STEP in earlier deliverables. In addition to this 'sense of community', some young people interviewed commented that the STEP platform is very useful in developing a **'sense of responsibility'** for the environment amongst young people.
- This also ties in with the 'sense of empowerment' and 'efficacy' already mentioned and is linked to trust factors. For the Pilots a good mix of online and offline (real-world) community building events and actions is a good starting point for building up this sense of community among the young citizens. All Pilots reported that they are spending time at such community events to try and raise awareness of the project and the platform.

Fig 3.1 A sample of some of the images posted to the Hatay Platform conveying the 'sense of community'

4 References

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5 Appendices

Appendix A: Interview Questions

Young European Citizens Questions:

- Demographic Questions: Age / City/ Municipality live in / occupation
Can you tell us how you became involved with the STEP eParticipation pilot trial.
 - How did you hear about it?
 - What made you want to get involved?
 - Have you been involved in a similar eParticipation activity before or is this the first time?
- Do you think that the opinions of young people are already adequately considered in your municipality?
 - Do you think that STEP will help to improve this issue?
- Was the process of (add in correct process, eg consultation) fully explained to you at the start?
- Do you think the timing of the process was adequate? (did you have enough time to participate fully / did you feel rushed?)
- What did you think of the STEP platform in general? Then specifically what did you think of..
 - Attractiveness?
 - Usability?
 - Interest – ie content.?
- For the specific eParticipation process you took part in (call for ideas / consultation process / e-Petitions / Round Table) what would you say was the best thing about taking part?
 - And the worst thing?
- In your opinion how could it have been made better?
- Did you use the social media mining tool? If yes.....
 - Did you find it useful
 - How regularly did you use it
 - What was the best thing about the tool
 - And the worst thing?
 - Any suggestions for improvement.
- Do you think you are more or less likely to participate in a similar eParticipation activity after taking part in the STEP pilot study? Reason?
- What level of interaction did you achieve on the platform? (did you speak to other YEC's, discuss anything with people from a different city? etc.)
- Did you share any information with others on the platform? If yes what was it and how did you share? ie on the platform / via other social media sites?)
- Did you feel that the information provided was trustworthy? Probe a little more here if necessary. political agenda etc.

- Do you think that the platform could help to develop a ‘sense of community’ for your local municipality?
 - Do you think that this would help to increase young people’s level of engagement?
- Anything else that you would like to comment on or share with us about your experience?

Thank Participant for taking part and ask if they would like to be informed on future developments regarding the project.

Public Officer Questions:

- Demographic Questions: Age / City/ Municipality live in / occupation
- Prior to the STEP project do you think that the opinions of young people were adequately considered in your municipality?
 - Do you think that STEP will help to improve this issue?
- Which process(es) did you set up / participate in?
- For this process (eg call for ideas) do you think the timing was adequate? (ie enough to enable you to use the platform and to give young people enough time to participate fully ?)
- What did you think of the STEP platform in general, was the experience positive / negative or a mixture of both ? Then specifically what did you think of..
 - Attractiveness?
 - Usability?
 - Interest – ie content?.
- Were you in charge of setting up a specific eParticipation process? If Yes..
 - How did you find the admin features?
 - Did you watch the training videos beforehand?
 - Did you have to seek assistance at any point?
 - Was the help provided useful / enough for you to achieve your goals
- For the specific eParticipation process you took part in (call for ideas / consultation process / e-Petitions / Round Table) what would you say was the best thing about taking part?
 - And the worst thing?
- In your opinion how could it have been made better?
- Did you use the social media mining tool? If yes.....
 - Did you find it useful?
 - How regularly did you use it?
 - What was the best thing about the tool?
 - And the worst thing?
 - Any suggestions for improvement.
- Compared to the old way of engaging with young people on environmental matters, Do you think that using the STEP platform is a better way? Reason?
- What level of interaction with young people did you achieve on the platform? (did you discuss anything other people
- Do you think that the platform could help to develop a ‘sense of community’ for your local municipality?
 - Do you think that this would help to increase young people’s level of engagement?

D5.1: Definition of STEP Pilots and Evaluation Methodology

- Do you think that the platform has helped to promote trust between young people and policy makers / public officers?
- Anything else that you would like to comment on or share with us about your experience with STEP?

Thank Participant for taking part.